

On the Quantum Mechanical and Temporal Origins of Entropy

Exploring the Interplay between the Cosmological
Arrow of Time, Thermodynamic Arrow of Time and
Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle

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Abstract

In this study, we explore the possibility of understanding the increase in the entropy of our universe as a consequence of microscopic uncertainty, as dictated by the uncertainty principle in quantum mechanics. The question of the arrow of time is also addressed: whether the arrow of time is a result of the second law of thermodynamics or the other way round. The most widely accepted view, as of now, is that entropy is responsible for the unidirectional nature of time. However, in this report, we argue that the cosmological arrow of time – which is a result of the expansion of the universe – comes first, and the second law of thermodynamics and the thermodynamic arrow of time follow. And while quantum uncertainty might not be directly responsible for driving the increase in entropy, it provides the foundational framework that allows entropy to be defined and to evolve meaningfully in our universe.

Keywords: Entropy, Uncertainty principle, Cosmological arrow of time, Thermodynamic arrow of time, Information, Statistical mechanics, Quantum mechanics

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Introduction

In the early days, it was believed that the universe is like a huge machine which runs according to the laws of classical physics, and if the state of motion of an object (its position and momentum) is known at one point of time, it could be determined at any other point of time in the past or the future. Since it was believed that in principle, it is possible to measure to any degree of accuracy the properties of a system, a complete knowledge of the state of motion of the system at any point in time is not forbidden. This implies that if we could somehow know the states of motion of every particle in the universe at one point in time, we could predict, at least in principle, their state of motion at any other point in time, whether in the past or the future. This idea is known as determinism. However, with the advent of quantum mechanics, determinism was challenged.

The Uncertainty Principle in Quantum Mechanics

According to Louis de Broglie's hypothesis, matter has a wave nature; every particle has a wave associated with it that is spread out over some distance. This can be roughly linked to the idea in quantum mechanics that particles have a probability of existing at more than one position before they are observed, or in other words, before a measurement of their position is carried out. This is technically referred to as quantum superposition. We will always find the particle at some definite location after the measurement. But if we measure it again, we may find the particle at a different location. And this is not due to any experimental error. Quantum mechanics asserts through the uncertainty principle that we cannot, even in theory, predict the precise location of a particle. The uncertainty principle is a consequence of the fact that the wave function describing a particle is not a localized wave, but rather a superposition of waves. A certain measurement of position would require a localized wave.

In quantum mechanics, the wave function of a system essentially contains all the information that can be known about that system. However, by itself the wave function has no physical meaning. The square of the modulus of the wave function can be interpreted as some probability (or probability density, more appropriately). The wave function of a particle roughly translates to the amplitude of the quantum mechanical wave describing the particle, and is a function of both position and time in general. It is allowed to take on both positive and negative values, and is a complex quantity in general. However, since probability is always a real and positive quantity, we interpret the square of its modulus as the probability of finding the particle at some given position and some given point in

time. We do not usually speak about finding a particle at a specific point in spacetime, owing to the uncertainty principle. A more meaningful question to ask is: What is the probability of finding this particle within the region in space between x to $x + dx$? If $\psi(x, t)$ is the wave function that describes the particle at position x and time t (assume a one-dimensional space for simplicity), then the answer to this question would be $|\psi(x, t)|^2 dx$. Thus, $|\psi(x, t)|^2$ can be thought of as some probability density.

The uncertainty principle in quantum mechanics, proposed by Werner Heisenberg, states that it is impossible to simultaneously determine both the position and momentum of a particle with a hundred percent accuracy. To qualitatively understand this, let us consider a simple thought experiment. To locate the position of a particle, we must shine light on it. To locate a microscopic particle (like an electron) accurately, we need a high energy (or low wavelength) light, so that it can interact with the particle and locate it (we can predict the location of the electron by observing the light that is scattered by it). However, high energy light will inevitably change the momentum of the particle after the interaction. Thus, if we want to measure the position accurately, the momentum of the particle will be uncertain (it cannot be measured accurately), and the converse is also true. Light does bounce off trees and houses and cars, but these are huge things compared to microscopic particles, and the effect is not noticeable.

It is important to realize that it is not the case that in the absence of light, an electron has well-defined position and momentum. Even when the electron is left to itself, its velocity and position change unpredictably from one moment to the next [1]. This uncertainty is not due to any technological limitations (like poor resolving power of our measuring instruments). According to quantum mechanics, this uncertainty is an inherent feature of the universe; and since we cannot even precisely determine the state (position and momentum) of a single particle, any hope of determinism is lost.

Just like position and momentum, both the energy and lifetime of a particle also cannot be simultaneously known with full accuracy. It is possible for microscopic particles to pop up and then vanish. The period of time for which the particle remains in existence, or its lifetime, is linked to its energy. The more accurately we know the energy of the particle, the less precisely can we know its lifetime, and vice versa. We can also think of it like this: to measure the energy of the particle precisely (very less uncertainty in energy measurement), we need to carry out the measurement for a longer amount of time (more uncertainty in time measurement). In fact, since vacuum is not fully devoid of energy according to

quantum mechanics, it is possible for particles to ‘borrow’ energy from vacuum for a short amount of time. The more energy a particle borrows, the sooner it must return it, meaning it must have a very short lifetime. These predictions are not purely theoretical; for example, experimental evidence of these ‘virtual particles’ has been observed in the Casimir effect, first predicted by Hendrik Casimir [2].

Mathematically, the uncertainty principle is expressed as:

$$\Delta x \Delta p_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}$$

This inequality simply says that the uncertainty in position measurement Δx , multiplied with the uncertainty in momentum measurement along that same direction Δp_x , must always be greater than or equal to a non-zero constant, $\hbar/2$ (\hbar is called the reduced Planck’s constant). To satisfy this inequality, smaller the value of Δx (Δp_x), larger the value of Δp_x (Δx). And since $\hbar/2$ is a non-zero constant, neither Δx nor Δp_x can be zero (the uncertainties in position or momentum cannot fully vanish); that would imply an infinite uncertainty in the other measurement (which makes no sense physically, because then the behavior of the particle becomes entirely random).

In terms of energy and time, the uncertainty principle can be written as:

$$\Delta E \Delta t \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}$$

These pairs of variables (position-momentum and energy-time) are known as canonically-conjugate variables. The more precisely we know the value of one of these variables, the less the information we can have about the other variable in the pair.

Richard Feynman stated the uncertainty principle in an alternative (and arguably more general) form: “Any determination of the alternative taken by a process capable of following more than one alternative destroys the interference between alternatives” [3, 4].

It can be shown that Heisenberg’s original statement about there being a minimum uncertainty in measurements of canonically-conjugate variables logically implies Feynman’s conclusion. Let us consider the double-slit experiment (using electrons) to illustrate this. Unlike classical physics, quantum physics cannot assign a unique trajectory to a particle moving between two points in spacetime. There are many possible trajectories of the evolution of a quantum system from a fixed initial state to a fixed final state. The double-slit experiment using electrons is a slightly modified version of Young’s double-slit experiment; the

major difference being here we replace the light source in Young's original double-slit experiment with an electron source, with electrons being fired at the screen with the two slits. The experimental setup is shown below. Some of the electrons that are fired will pass through the slits and hit the final screen. By keeping track of the different positions on the final screen hit by the electrons, we can determine the intensity of the electrons on the final screen (after a sufficiently large number of electrons have been fired at the double-slit).

Figure 1: Experimental set-up of the double-slit experiment with electrons. (Source: Wikipedia.)

Classically, we would expect that the most probable location for finding the electrons on the final screen to be the areas on the screen directly behind the two slits. Since some electrons may get deflected through an angle at the slits, we might find a few electrons at other positions as well; but the maximum intensity of electrons would be directly behind the two slits, as illustrated below.

Figure 2: Expected electron intensity on the final screen in the double-slit experiment. (Source: Albert Hoffmann, HAL Open Science.)

But in reality, we obtain a pattern which is similar to the interference pattern observed with light in Young's double-slit experiment, as shown below (Figure 3). There are alternate regions where electrons are found (maxima) and where they are not found (minima). The region of the central maxima is not accessible to most of the electrons in the classical picture. The results of this experiment defy a classical explanation. We get some hint that in addition to the classical paths, there are other possible paths contributing to the overall electron intensity on the final screen. This serves as a good illustration of the notion of alternate paths of evolution of quantum particles (in this case, electrons), and the uncertainty stemming from it. It should be noted that this interference pattern is a certain outcome of the experiment; if a sufficiently large number of electrons are made to pass through the slits, we will always get this pattern on the final screen. The uncertainty is in the path of a single electron between the source and the final screen, which cannot be uniquely determined.

*Figure 3: Observed electron intensity on the final screen in the double-slit experiment.
(Source: Albert Hoffmann, HAL Open Science.)*

If we keep only one slit open in the above experiment, then we get the greatest number of electrons directly behind the open slit, as illustrated in Figure 4. If we keep slit 1 open and slit 2 closed, the corresponding intensity distribution is P_1 ; if we keep only slit 2 open, then the corresponding intensity distribution is P_2 . Mathematically, P_1 is defined as the square of modulus of the amplitude for the case when only slit 1 is open, say $|\psi_1|^2$. Similarly, $P_2 = |\psi_2|^2$, where ψ_2 is the amplitude for the case when only slit 2 is open. Now, if we keep both the slits open, the resulting intensity distribution P_{12} is not the sum of P_1 and P_2 , as we would have expected classically. Rather, to calculate P_{12} , we first sum up the

corresponding amplitudes and then square the modulus of this sum. This is in accordance with the superposition principle.

$$P_{12} = |\psi_{12}|^2 = |\psi_1 + \psi_2|^2$$

Figure 4: P_1 represents the probability distribution of electrons on the final screen when only slit 1 is kept open (slit 2 is closed). P_2 represents the same when only slit 2 is kept open. P_{12} is the probability distribution when both the slits are open. (Source: Foundations of Science.

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The superposition principle in quantum mechanics is analogous to the superposition principle in classical wave theory. For waves in classical physics, the superposition principle essentially governs the interference of the waves. It states that the amplitude (or displacement) of the resulting wave when many waves interfere is the sum of the amplitudes (or displacements) of the individual waves. In quantum mechanics, we replace “amplitude” or “displacement” with “probability amplitude.” Probability amplitudes in quantum mechanics obey the superposition principle as long as there is no real measurement being made on the system when it is at an intermediate state between the initial and final states. Otherwise, the interference is destroyed and the superposition principle no longer holds. In such cases, the total probability is simply the sum of the individual probabilities. For instance, when we are keeping only one slit open in the double-slit experiment, the interference is destroyed. In this case, the resultant intensity distribution, say P , is given by:

$$P = P_1 + P_2 = |\psi_1|^2 + |\psi_2|^2$$

In the double-slit experiment, if we want to detect which slit an electron went through, we have to make a physical measurement on the electron between its initial state (when it is in the electron gun) and its final state (when it has reached the final screen), which will inevitably destroy the interference pattern. This is the alternate statement of the uncertainty principle.

We can try determining whether an electron passed through slit 1 or slit 2 by putting detectors of sufficiently weak light in front of the slits. Since the light is sufficiently weak, we will observe scattering of light in the detector placed at slit 1 if an electron passes through slit 1, and observe no scattering in the detector placed at slit 2 for that electron. However, since the electron is forced to physically interact with light in its trajectory, it is not surprising that its trajectory has been altered, and so are the probabilities of this electron appearing at different positions on the final screen. In this case, the interference is destroyed and the final distribution is the one shown in Figure 2.

Now, let us consider a modified version of this experiment, in which the screen containing the two slits is free to move vertically. Let us fix a position x between the two slits on the final screen, labelled 'DETECTOR' in the figure below. It is clear from the figure that to end up at position x on the final screen, the electron must deflect downward if it passes through slit 1, and deflect upward if it passes through slit 2. There will be a change in the vertical component of the electron's momentum in both the cases, and the slit screen will move in the opposite direction to the deflection of the electron, and hence gain a non-zero momentum in both the cases, as demanded by the law of conservation of momentum. In the figure below, Δp_x is the magnitude of the difference in these momentum values (when the electron passes through slit 1 and slit 2). This difference in the momentum, Δp_x , can be precisely measured by observing the movement of the slit screen, without disturbing the electrons.

Figure 5: A modified version of the double-slit experiment using electrons, where the slit screen is free to move vertically. (Source: *The Feynman Lectures on Physics, Volume III: Quantum Mechanics.*)

Now, assuming the uncertainty principle (as originally stated by Heisenberg) to be true, since we know Δp_x accurately, we cannot measure the exact position of the slit screen, and as a result the difference in the exact positions of the slits Δx , with sufficient accuracy. This means the positions of the slits would vary for each electron as they are fired, and hence the positions of the maxima (and minima) on the final screen cannot be fixed. This would destroy the interference pattern. This qualitatively shows why the statement: “Any determination of the alternative taken by a process capable of following more than one alternative destroys the interference between alternatives” can be treated as equivalent to Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle, since we showed why this must logically follow if we assume $\Delta x \Delta p_x \geq \hbar/2$.

It would be interesting to discuss another thought experiment with regard to the uncertainty principle. Albert Einstein tried to challenge the uncertainty principle using this thought experiment [5]. He imagined a box of light. A single photon could, in principle, be released from the box by a clockwork shutter, and the exact time be recorded. The box can be weighed before and after the photon is released, and using the change in mass, Einstein’s equation $E = \Delta mc^2$ can be employed to calculate accurately the energy of the photon. This apparently seems to imply that it is possible to measure both the energy and the time accurately and at the same time. However, assuming that the box is placed in some gravitational field (for instance, the Earth’s gravitational field), Niels Bohr pointed out that when the photon would be released, the box would recoil, creating an uncertainty in the position of the box within Earth’s gravitational field, which (ironically from Einstein’s own theory of general relativity) would create further uncertainty in time. This saves the uncertainty principle.

The uncertainty principle imposes a fundamental limit on the amount of information that can be known about a system. It plays a central role in quantum mechanics. We may ask, how is it possible at all to make reasonably good predictions about the behavior of large (macroscopic) bodies, when it is not possible to exactly predict the behavior of the microscopic particles that comprise these macroscopic bodies? A rough understanding of this might be obtained by looking at the law of large numbers. We cannot predict the outcome of the toss of a single coin. It is 50% heads and 50% tails. We cannot predict whether the outcome of a particular coin toss would be a head or a tail. But if we toss a coin 10000 times, we will, without fail, see that the number of heads as well as tails will both converge to 5000. If we toss an unbiased coin 1000 times, it is very unlikely that we get 900 heads and 100 tails, although it is much more likely that we might get 9 heads and 1 tail if we toss the coin only 10 times. So, although we cannot make accurate predictions about a single coin toss (or a very small number

of coin tosses), it is perfectly possible to make good predictions about a large number of coin tosses. In the context of quantum mechanics, everything in the macroscopic world is made up of a really large number of microscopic particles. However, the question of how macroscopic behavior emerges from the laws of quantum mechanics governing the constituent microscopic particles, is a fundamental question that has not been fully answered yet, and certainly deserves further attention.

Entropy in Statistical Mechanics

Statistical mechanics tries to understand large (macroscopic) systems in terms of the dynamics of the microscopic constituents, and with the help of probabilistic assumptions [6]. Although we can use quantum mechanics to study the behavior of a single microscopic particle (within the limits set by the uncertainty principle), it becomes practically impossible to apply quantum mechanics to explain the behavior of large, classical systems. Statistical mechanics makes it possible to effectively understand the macroscopic properties observed in such large systems in terms of the dynamics of the microscopic constituents. Although thermodynamics by itself is an empirical science (meaning it mostly deals with macroscopic properties that can be experimentally measured), statistical mechanics successfully proves many familiar results of classical thermodynamics, starting from the microscopic principles. A major portion of statistical mechanics is concerned with systems in equilibrium; it is much easier to study systems that are in equilibrium with their surroundings. However, most of the systems around us are not in perfect equilibrium. In fact, if everything around us was in perfect equilibrium with the surroundings, they could not exchange energy and information with the surroundings, and nothing would occur. It would be a very boring world!

The concept of entropy is one of the most important concepts in statistical mechanics, and in fact all of physics. It is commonly said that the more the disorder, the more the entropy. However, this simple definition of entropy can be deceptive without a deeper understanding. According to the second law of thermodynamics, the entropy of a closed system (a system that does not exchange energy and information with its surroundings) must always either remain the same or increase. Entropy can be defined as the number of ways a particular state can be achieved. This does not mean just the number of ways the different parts of the system can be arranged (spatial configurations). We also have to take into account the velocities and energies of all the parts of the system at a given point in time.

In our universe, the overall entropy is increasing with time. It might seem that the entropy increases in our universe because the universe is expanding and more and more spatial configurations become possible within the volume of the universe due to the expansion. However, entropy does not depend solely on the number of different spatial configurations possible. Even if the universe were contracting, the overall entropy could have increased due to the fact that every object in the universe could emit radiation, which contains energy, thus increasing the number of possible energy configurations of the universe, since the radiation (or photons) would spread throughout the universe and disperse energy everywhere.

Equilibrium refers to the state with the maximum entropy. It is a natural tendency of systems that are not in equilibrium to try to reach an equilibrium state (highest entropy state) over time. As we have discussed, the overall entropy of our universe increases. If we forcibly try to prevent a system from reaching equilibrium (the highest entropy state), we must be aware of the states of the particles of the system to achieve this feat (the information of the states in our brains can be thought of as a factor that contributes to the increase of the overall entropy), and we must supply some external energy (do some work) to the system to prevent it from attaining an equilibrium state. This system can no longer be regarded as a closed system, since there is some energy input from the surroundings. The second law of thermodynamics states that the entropy of closed systems must not decrease; however, for open systems, a local decrease in entropy is perfectly allowed, as long as the total entropy of the system plus surroundings increases. A common scenario often employed to illustrate the idea of entropy is that if we have an untidy room, it is in a high entropy state, whereas a neat and clean room will have a low entropy. Now, it is perfectly possible for us to clean the room and decrease the entropy of the room. But we have to spend a lot of energy to do the cleaning, which contributes to the increase of the overall entropy.

Now, let us properly define entropy. We may define entropy as a measure of disorder in a non-technical fashion, but that is not exactly so. It is true that an untidy room is in a higher entropy state as compared to a neat and clean room; but this is not a very accurate description of the concept of entropy. Let us consider a better example, even at the cost of the simplicity of the previous illustration. If we have five differently colored balls and two boxes, the lowest entropy state would be achieved if we keep all five balls in one box and thus, no balls in the other. There are only two ways in which we can achieve this configuration: either put all the balls in the first box keeping the second box empty, or vice versa. This indicates low entropy. Also, this state is clearly not an equilibrium configuration, because the 'concentration' of the balls is higher on one side. If we decide to keep two balls in one box and three in the other, by

taking into account the five different colors, the number of ways we can achieve this state goes up drastically, indicating a higher entropy. And in this case, a near-equilibrium state is attained. This is a beautiful illustration of how increasing entropy corresponds to the system moving toward equilibrium.

Figure 6: The ordered arrangement on the left becomes disordered over time due to increase in entropy. (Source: Jack Westin.)

Since everything tends to reach an equilibrium state, we may argue (within the limits of statistical mechanics) that the probability of finding a system in equilibrium is the maximum. And since entropy increases over time as the system evolves, and the equilibrium state has the maximum entropy, it seems there must be a positive correlation between entropy of a state and the probability of finding a system in that state (and if this state is the equilibrium state, the corresponding entropy is maximum). Based on this assumption, Ludwig Boltzmann arrived at a mathematical expression for the entropy of a state that we find the system in [7]:

$$S = k \ln(W) + C$$

Here, S is the entropy of the state, W is the number of possible ways we can arrive at this state, and k and C are constants. Based on further arguments, it was showed that $C = 0$ and the value of the constant k was also determined. It is now known as Boltzmann's constant, k_B . Thus, we can write:

$$S = k_B \ln(W)$$

Although W is dubbed “thermodynamic probability,” it is clearly not a fraction between 0 and 1, and is nothing like ordinary probability. The more the number of possible ways allowed for the state we are concerned with, the higher the value of W (it is more probable to find the system in that state), and the higher the value of the corresponding entropy S .

It should be noted that the above equation is applicable only for systems in equilibrium or near-equilibrium with their surroundings. In non-equilibrium systems, the macroscopic properties of the system keep changing and the relation between entropy and thermodynamic probability is complicated. Further, it is important to note that although it is practically impossible to keep track of this continuous change in the properties of a non-equilibrium system, this ‘uncertainty’ is not an inherent property of such macroscopic systems, unlike the uncertainty in the measurements of position and momentum (or energy and time) in quantum mechanics.

Information: Quantum Unitarity and Statistical Entropy

We are now interested in searching for something that might act as a bridge between the two fields discussed above: quantum mechanics (mainly, Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle) and statistical mechanics (mainly entropy). As we will explain, information could serve as such a bridge.

The principle of unitarity in quantum mechanics can be expressed in many ways, but it definitely is a fundamental feature of quantum mechanics [8, 9, 10, 11]. As we have already seen, we deal with wave functions (or probability amplitudes) in quantum mechanics. Let $\langle b|a\rangle$ denote the probability amplitude associated with the event that a quantum system changes from initial state \mathbf{a} to final state \mathbf{b} . In quantum mechanics, we associate an observable corresponding to every measurable (every parameter that can be measured, for example, position, momentum etc.). On performing a measurement on an observable, we get an outcome which defines the state of the system. The state of the system cannot be specified before the measurement, but after this measurement the system ‘collapses’ to the state defined by the observed outcome. If we perform a second measurement (on the same or a different observable), we will get a different outcome, which will define the new state of the system. In $\langle b|a\rangle$, \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are the outcomes of corresponding observables \hat{a} and \hat{b} . For example, if \hat{a} is the velocity observable for the system, a measurement on \hat{a} will yield an outcome that corresponds to the velocity of the system. Similarly, if \hat{b} is the position observable for the system under consideration, a measurement on \hat{b} will yield an outcome that corresponds to the position of that system. Suppose we make a measurement on observable \hat{a} and obtain outcome \mathbf{a} . Then on the same system, we perform another measurement on observable \hat{b} and obtain outcome \mathbf{b} . Then $\langle b|a\rangle$ represents the probability amplitude of this event, in which we perform two subsequent measurements of observables \hat{a} and \hat{b} respectively, and obtain outcomes \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} respectively. The square of the modulus of $\langle b|a\rangle$, i.e., $|\langle b|a\rangle|^2$

gives the probability of obtaining outcomes **a** and **b** on performing two subsequent measurements on \hat{a} and \hat{b} respectively. Now, the mathematical framework of quantum mechanics asserts that $|\langle b|a\rangle|^2 = |\langle a|b\rangle|^2$, which means the probability of getting outcomes **a** and **b** on performing two subsequent measurements on \hat{a} and \hat{b} respectively, is the same as the probability of the reverse event (getting outcomes **b** and **a** on performing two subsequent measurements on \hat{b} and \hat{a} respectively), for the same system. This is referred to as time symmetry. There is no arrow of time in the laws of quantum mechanics; it is, in principle, perfectly possible to ‘undo’ a quantum event. The probability of a ‘quantum coffee mug’ falling from the table and breaking to pieces is the same as the probability of it picking the broken pieces up all by itself and reassembling into its original, unbroken configuration on the table. This behavior is not observed in large objects; of course, we would not expect a real broken coffee mug to repair itself.

All of this can be captured by the statement that time evolution of a quantum system is always unitary (hence the name “unitarity”). While discussing the detailed mathematical framework of the canonical formulation of quantum mechanics is both irrelevant and beyond the scope of this report, we can outline the important points. Every state of a quantum system can be thought of as a vector in a special type of vector space (the details are not discussed here), and can be represented by a column matrix. And every transformation of the system from an initial state to a final state can be represented by a square matrix (called the transformation matrix). Let us, for simplicity, assume our quantum system exists in two dimensions, and the initial and final states **a** and **b** are represented by the matrices:

$$a = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad b = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Let us define a transformation matrix **T** that transforms the system from state **a** to state **b**:

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} \end{bmatrix}$$

Mathematically, the transformation can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The transformation matrix represents a quantum operator, and we can define an operator for every observable. Now, although the mathematics of quantum mechanics involves complex numbers, the outcome of any physical measurement

must always be real, to satisfy which all quantum operators must be Hermitian matrices (the mathematical proof of why this must be so is skipped in this report, and again, it is not strictly relevant to the aim of this report). The quantum operator linked with the energy observable is called the Hamiltonian operator, which, we now know, must be Hermitian. This requires the operator representing the time evolution of the quantum system to be unitary (its representation must be a unitary matrix). Unitarity (of the time evolution of quantum systems) ensures all the required conditions are satisfied: the outcomes of the measurements are real, the probability $|\langle b|a\rangle|^2$ is equal to the reverse probability $|\langle a|b\rangle|^2$ and the sum of all probabilities of all the possibilities is one.

But what has unitarity to do with information? Unitarity ensures that information is conserved during the evolution of any quantum system. We have already seen that owing to time symmetry, it is theoretically possible for us to ‘undo’ a quantum event; or in other words, the information associated with the quantum system is preserved over time as it evolves. If information was lost in the process, it would not be possible to ‘undo’ the event, and $|\langle b|a\rangle|^2 \neq |\langle a|b\rangle|^2$.

Next, let us look at entropy and information. We can think of information in terms of reduction of uncertainty. If someone is about to send us a message, we are uncertain about what the message would say. But once we read it, the information in the message reduces our uncertainty. To determine the contents of the message, one might ask questions that can have only two answers: yes or no. Since the answers to these questions can be either yes or no, we say that each answer contains one bit of information. For questions that cannot be answered using just yes or no, we can say that the information associated with it is the minimum number of questions we need to ask whose answer can be either yes or no, to be able to determine the answer. For example, the answer to the question “What is your name?” cannot be yes or no. However, we may ask questions like “Does your name start with the letter A?,” “Is your first name five-lettered?” etc., and after a sufficient number of such questions that can be answered in yes or no, we can uniquely determine the name. Let us say there are N possible messages that could have been sent. The information (I) in the message is the number of bits needed to represent the message, and can be mathematically defined as:

$$I = \log_2 N$$

The logarithm is taken to the base two simply because we obtain information by asking questions that can have only two answers (yes or no). Notice that the above equation is similar to the equation for entropy: $S = k_B \ln(W)$.

Shannon's entropy [12, 13] is defined in a similar manner, but there are crucial differences. Claude Shannon's motivation was to quantify the average uncertainty in an event, and this is directly correlated with the information associated with the system. By uncertainty, here we mean the 'surprise' associated with the outcome of the event. The outcome of rolling a die contains more 'surprise' and uncertainty than tossing a coin, because there are six possible outcomes of rolling a die and only two possible outcomes of a coin toss. Shannon's entropy is simply a measure of the average 'surprise' associated with the event, and it is defined as the information associated with each possible outcome multiplied by the corresponding probability of that outcome, summed over all possible outcomes. Mathematically, Shannon's entropy is defined as:

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2 p_i = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2 \left(\frac{1}{p_i} \right)$$

Here, the Shannon entropy H is the average information content (or average uncertainty) associated with the event, which has n number of possible outcomes (hence the summation index i runs from 1 to n). The expression $\log_2 \left(\frac{1}{p_i} \right)$ is the information associated with the i -th outcome. For simplicity, if we assume that the probability of all the outcomes is the same, p , then the number of outcomes must be $1/p$, to ensure the total probability of all the outcomes is 1. Thus, in this case, since the number of outcomes is $1/p$, the information associated with an outcome must be $\log_2 \left(\frac{1}{p} \right)$. This same expression holds even when all the outcomes do not have the same probability, hence the $\log_2 \left(\frac{1}{p_i} \right)$ is the information associated with the i -th outcome. To obtain the average information, we multiply this expression with the corresponding probability (of that outcome) and sum over all the possibilities. Here, all p_i s are mathematical probabilities, meaning they are fractions lying between 0 and 1. In Boltzmann's expression for entropy, however, W (the thermodynamic probability) was the number of possible ways the state in question can be achieved, and clearly W is not a fraction. When expressed as $-\sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2 p_i$, the negative sign in Shannon's entropy takes care of the fact that the logarithm of a fraction between 0 and 1 is negative.

In essence, the more the uncertainty, the more the information and the entropy. We can also think of information like this: say we are trying to completely describe two events A and B. The more different the events are from each other, the more the amount of information we need to describe the events fully, so that we can tell them apart. For example, suppose A and B are similar in all respects except one. Then, we need to only describe either A or B and mention this one

difference. If A and B are different in two aspects, we need more information to fully describe A and B, and so on. In some sense, information is what helps us distinguish between different objects in the universe. For instance, it is the information of the arrangement of electrons and number of protons and neutrons in an atom that determines whether the atom is a hydrogen atom or a carbon atom.

The more the randomness (or uncertainty), the more the information. Consider two strings (just sequences of ones and zeros): 11111111 and 0000000. These strings contain less information than the string 01100011111111011100000000101. We can describe 11111111 as “eight ones” (and 0000000 as “seven zeros”). Such a simple description is not possible for 01100011111111011100000000101. This is a more random string, as compared to 11111111 or 0000000. Since we know randomness can be linked to entropy, we intuitively see why it is possible to define some quantity much similar to entropy for these strings, and why this ‘entropy’ will have a much higher value for the third string, to describe which we need much more information than the first two strings. Thus, entropy and information are not independent: they are interlinked ideas. Shannon’s entropy forms the basis of the information theory of entropy, according to which, as we have seen, entropy is the measure of the average amount of information needed to describe an event, while considering all possible outcomes.

The relation between entropy and information is more complicated, however, than it might appear to be at first glance. It is not true that with increasing entropy, the information would keep increasing (recall that quantum mechanics claims the information associated with any system must be preserved). The maximum entropy state (equilibrium state) of a system need not correspond to a state with a high amount of information. The maximum entropy state is the most random state. In principle, it is completely random and disordered. This means, of course, there can be no order in the system; in its entirety it must be indistinguishable in all directions, at all points in space and over time. Imagine a very large box of gas particles in their maximum entropy state. Although the gas particles move about and collide with one another randomly, the entire system looks the same in all directions and over time. If we further assume the box containing the gas stretches infinitely in all directions, we see that it would be impossible for someone inside this box to distinguish one direction from another, or one point in space from another. And this does not change over time. A special feature of a system in its maximum entropy state is that its entropy cannot increase any further (it is already at its maximum entropy state). The maximum entropy state, which is a state of complete disorder, is not governed by any local laws (laws that apply to specific regions inside the system, or perhaps laws that treat different directions

differently). If there are local laws within the system, we could distinguish different directions and also distinguish between different regions within the system. The absence of local laws means we do not need much information to describe this completely random system. Think about nothingness, just void, empty space, which is the same at all points in space and time, just like the completely disordered state we have been discussing above. We do not need much information to describe nothingness; there is nothing to describe. The same goes for a completely random system; we do not need any additional information to describe any 'asymmetry' or special feature in the system, since it is globally the same at all points in space and time. Thus, ignoring the physical description of the constituents (in our example, gas particles) of the system, both nothingness and complete randomness (maximum entropy state) are informationally equivalent at a fundamental level.

We have discussed the relation between entropy and information, and the relation between information and uncertainty has also been discussed. Of course, the 'uncertainty' that we mentioned in relation to information is not the same as the uncertainty we encountered in Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. However, it is not only interesting, but equally important to explore possible links between microscopic uncertainty in quantum mechanics and macroscopic entropy in statistical mechanics. While we have different branches of physics that apply to different length scales and energy scales, these branches are not completely independent of one another, and together they describe the same physical universe. Many of the intersections between these branches have been or are being explored in the hope of obtaining a more complete and more fundamental understanding of the universe.

Microstates, Entropy and the Uncertainty Principle

In classical mechanics, the trajectory of a particle – the path it follows through space over time – is drawn in the configuration space. Let us consider a particle in a one-dimensional space (represented by the x axis). At every point in time t , the particle will be at some position x . The state of the particle can be represented by a point on position-vs-time space (configuration space). If we plot the points corresponding to all the states of the particle as it moves through space over time, we will trace out the trajectory of the particle. In statistical mechanics, however, it is more useful to study the dynamics of a system in phase space [4], rather than in configuration space.

Phase Space and Microstates

Consider the same scenario: a particle moving in a one-dimensional space. For this particle, the phase space will be a two-dimensional momentum-vs-position space. Every point on the phase space represents a microstate of the particle. We can draw a trajectory on the phase space over time, although this is not the movement of the particle through real space (hence it is not the trajectory of the particle in the real, physical world). If we are dealing with a real particle in three-dimensional space, the corresponding phase space would be six-dimensional, because we would need three spatial coordinates (say x , y and z), and three coordinates to represent the momenta across each of these independent spatial directions (p_x , p_y and p_z).

To completely determine the state of a particle, we need to know its position and momentum (or velocity, since momentum can be calculated by multiplying the velocity with the mass of the particle) at each point in time. For a single particle, we can obtain this information just by looking at the trajectory of the particle in real space (configuration space). The trajectory on configuration space is a position-vs-time curve, the slope of which gives the velocity of the particle. However, when we have a macroscopic system comprising a large number of microscopic particles in three dimensions (the kind of systems statistical mechanics deals with), it is extremely difficult to calculate the states of the microscopic particles (microstates) of the system as it evolves, if we work in real space. Phase space is defined in a way that each point on the phase space corresponding to a particle automatically contains information about the position and momentum of that particle, and effectively represents the complete state of the particle. Of course, the phase space is an abstract mathematical space, and is

not necessarily three dimensional. However, it is an extremely powerful formulation when dealing with systems made of a large number of particles.

We will now discuss a little more on phase space and microstates. To better understand phase space, let us look at a particle undergoing simple harmonic oscillation in one dimension (say, x). The kinetic energy of the particle would just be the classical expression $p^2/2m$, where p is the momentum and m the mass of the particle. The potential energy of a simple harmonic oscillator is given by $kx^2/2$. Thus, the total energy E of the particle is:

$$E = \frac{p^2}{2m} + \frac{kx^2}{2}$$

Dividing both sides of the above equation by E , we get:

$$1 = \frac{p^2}{2mE} + \frac{kx^2}{2E}$$

This is the equation of an ellipse on a p -vs- x space (p is the vertical axis, and x the horizontal axis). Thus, the phase trajectory of a single particle undergoing simple harmonic motion in one dimension is, in general, an ellipse. In the special case of $m = 1/k$, the trajectory will be a circle.

Figure 7: The circular trajectory in phase space of a particle (the green dot in the red block of mass hung by a spring) undergoing simple harmonic motion in one dimension. (Source: Wikipedia.)

Let us now consider the swinging of a pendulum, and we will not neglect the effect of friction. This motion is damped harmonic oscillation; the swinging of the pendulum can be represented by a sinusoidal wave with a decaying amplitude (due to friction). The corresponding phase diagram will be a circular curve that spirals inward to the origin (the mean position of the pendulum, where both the position and momentum are zero), since due to friction, the pendulum will eventually come to rest at its mean position.

Figure 8: Phase trajectory for a pendulum with friction. (Source: Cruz Jesson.)

Now, we will discuss the idea of microstate and macrostate in statistical mechanics [14]. Let us consider a box that is divided into two partitions; let the left partition be A and the right partition be B. We also have four distinguishable particles colored red, green, blue and yellow. Say we want a configuration in which there are three balls in the left partition A and one ball in B. We can achieve this configuration in four different ways, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 9: Four microstates corresponding to the same macrostate. (Source: Chemistry LibreTexts.)

Let us assume the color is a microscopic property of the balls, which cannot be directly measured by us. In other words, macroscopically the four cases shown in the above figure are the same. This defines the macrostate of the system: three

balls in A, one in B. If we talk about the microstate, however, the four cases above are distinct. Thus, there can be more than one microstate corresponding to the same macrostate (in this case, we see there can be four microstates for the same macrostate). For a real system, like a box containing a large number of gas particles, examples of macroscopic properties are temperature and volume. A given value of temperature, at a given instant of time, is a macrostate of this system. Macroscopic properties can be measured by us, and they are defined on the entire system. It is meaningless to ask: What is the temperature of that particular gas molecule? We can only ask: What is the temperature of this box of gas right now? Using statistical mechanics, we can show how these macroscopic properties arise from the behavior of the microscopic particles in the system. Temperature, for instance, is a collective effect of the vibration of the microscopic particles; the more vigorously the particles vibrate, the more would be the temperature of the system. This depends on the microscopic properties of the particles, like their positions and momenta (in other words, the microstate).

We have previously mentioned that every point on the phase space represents the complete microstate of the particle at a given instant of time. In three-dimensional space, we need three position coordinates: x , y , z , and three momentum coordinates: p_x , p_y , p_z to completely specify the position and momentum of a particle along all possible directions at a given instant of time. Hence, the phase space must be six-dimensional. For a system consisting of N particles, we need a phase space with $6N$ number of dimensions to completely describe the entire system, and a point in this space gives the complete state of the system at a given instant of time. As the system evolves with time, this phase point moves according to the equation of motion and draws out the phase trajectory.

Now, this system of N particles is a macroscopic system. The microstate of this system at any given instant of time is simply the collective states (positions and momenta) of all the N particles at that instant of time. In the next instant of time, all the particles will have moved by a little amount (since they possess momentum), some of them might collide with others and have their direction of motion changed. Thus, in general, the positions and momenta of all the N particles have changed in the next instant of time, and on the phase space, the phase point has moved to a new position.

Phase Cells and the Uncertainty Principle

Let us think about the system of N particles we have encountered above. We start by assuming that this system is in equilibrium. When we say this system is in equilibrium with its surroundings, we mean that there is no exchange of energy

or information between the system and the surroundings, and the macroscopic properties of the system, like its temperature, remain constant. However, the N microscopic particles are continuously moving randomly and colliding among each other. In other words, the macrostate of the system is fixed, but there are many possible microstates corresponding to this macrostate.

At this point, we are faced with an important question: How do we know the microstate of the system has changed? Suppose we know the microstate (the positions and momenta of all the N particles) at one instant of time. In the very next instant of time, the microstate will have changed by some infinitesimal amount, owing to the change in the positions and momenta of the particles. However, if we assume the microstate changes continuously through every instant of time, it would be impossible for us to keep track of this continuous change in microstate. Thus, we divide the phase space into a large number of volumes of some finite magnitude. Each such elementary volume is called a phase cell. This volume does not necessarily refer to the physical volume of some three-dimensional space, this is an elementary volume of the phase space (which can be more than three-dimensional, as we have discussed). All the points on the phase space lying inside the same phase cell correspond to the same microstate. We can say the microstate of the system has changed only if the phase point has moved to a different phase cell. This way, we discretize the phase space, and avoid the problem of dealing with the microstate of the system changing continuously and by infinitesimal amounts.

This division of the phase space into small, finite phase cells can, in fact, be attributed to the uncertainty principle. Let us recall that the phase space is essentially a momentum-vs-position space, and according to the uncertainty principle, we cannot measure both these quantities simultaneously with a hundred percent accuracy. If we assign a fixed point on the phase space to a particular microstate of the system, we imply that both the position and momentum of that state are simultaneously known perfectly, which is forbidden by the uncertainty principle.

Let us consider a n -dimensional space, and for simplicity, just one particle. To take into account the inherent uncertainty in position and momentum measurements of this system, we divide the phase space into identical phase cells of finite volume h^n . The constant h was initially assumed to be related to experimental limitations in our measurement, and classically it could be chosen to be as small as possible. Eventually with the development of quantum mechanics, it became clear that h is actually Planck's constant [15]. When $n = 1$

(one-dimensional space), the phase space for a single particle, that has been divided into phase cells, is shown below.

Figure 10: The phase space for a single particle in one-dimension has been divided into identical phase cells, one of which has been shaded. (Source: Peter Eastman, Stanford University.)

From the above figure, clearly, the volume of a single phase cell is $\delta x \delta p$, where δx and δp are the limiting uncertainties in position and momentum measurements of the particle, respectively. Note that in the above case, the phase space is two-dimensional, and $\delta x \delta p$ should be referred to as the area of the shaded square (phase cell); we use the word “volume” for phase cell in general. Anyway, from the uncertainty principle, we know that the limiting value of the product $\delta x \delta p$ should be of the order of Planck’s constant h . This is why we assume the volume of the phase cell, in this case, to be h (since the system is confined to one dimension, here $n = 1$, and $h^n = h$). If we consider a single particle in three dimensions, the phase space would be six-dimensional, and the volume of a phase cell would be h^3 . Let us say the three dimensions are x , y and z . Clearly, we would have three products $\delta x \delta p_x$, $\delta y \delta p_y$ and $\delta z \delta p_z$, where p_x , p_y and p_z are the momenta along the x , y and z directions respectively. This is why the total volume is h^3 (here the particle is in a three-dimensional space, so $n = 3$, and $h^n = h^3$).

Density of States and Entropy

The density of states [14] is most commonly defined as the number of quantum states that lie within a given energy range. In statistical mechanics terminology, the density of states refers to the number of microstates corresponding to a given macrostate of the system. “A given macrostate” may refer to a specified set of energy values of the system (a given energy range which contains a discrete set of energy values, since energy is quantized according to quantum mechanics). Essentially, our question is: How many possible microstates are present within the energy range E to $E + dE$? Since each phase cell corresponds to a unique microstate, we may slightly rephrase this question: How many phase cells in the phase space of the system correspond to microstates that correspond to energy values of the system between E and $E + dE$? It is important to realize that the constraint on the allowed energies (E to $E + dE$) essentially means we are considering a part of the entire phase space. If we put a constraint on the energy, we put a constraint on the momentum, since for a free particle of mass m , the momentum p and the energy E are related by:

$$E = \frac{p^2}{2m}$$

Differentiating both sides with respect to p , we get:

$$dE = \frac{p}{m} dp$$

The energy range E to $E + dE$ corresponds to a particular momentum range p to $p + dp$, which defines a small volume in the phase space, say dV – only the volume corresponding to which the values on the momentum axis lie within this momentum range. Now, the number of microstates corresponding to the energy range E to $E + dE$ is the number of phase cells that lie within this volume dV in the phase space, which is just the total volume in consideration dV divided by the elementary volume on the phase space h^3 (volume of a single phase cell, assume the number of dimensions $n = 3$).

Now, the volume dV on the phase space corresponds to a finite range of momentum as well as a finite range of positions. Considering the positions and momenta along all three directions, we can write:

$$dV = \iiint dx dy dz \iiint dp_x dp_y dp_z$$

The integrals have been defined over the corresponding energy range E to $E + dE$. The volume on the phase space available for the specified energy range is the

product of the physical volume (volume in the corresponding position space) $\iiint dx dy dz$ and the volume in the corresponding momentum space $\iiint dp_x dp_y dp_z$.

For a single particle in three-dimensional space, we can thus define the density of states (the number of microstates corresponding to the given energy range), say g , as:

$$g = \frac{\iiint dx dy dz \iiint dp_x dp_y dp_z}{h^3}$$

The numerator of the above expression is a finite, non-zero volume in the phase space of the system. The denominator is the Planck's constant raised to the third power, and is directly related to Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. Let us now ask an interesting question: What if the uncertainty principle was not true? That would mean we could measure both the position and momentum of a particle simultaneously with perfect accuracy. Mathematically, this means:

$$\Delta x \Delta p_x \geq 0$$

In other words, it would be possible for the product $\Delta x \Delta p_x$ to be zero. Comparing with $\Delta x \Delta p_x \geq \hbar/2$, we see that saying the uncertainty principle does not hold is equivalent to replacing $\hbar \rightarrow 0$; in other words, $h \rightarrow 0$, since the reduced Planck's constant \hbar is defined as $h/2\pi$.

As $h \rightarrow 0$, we see that the density of states $g \rightarrow \infty$. This means if the uncertainty principle was not true, there would be an infinite number of microstates corresponding to a given energy range E to $E + dE$. Of course, since $h \rightarrow 0$, the volume of a phase cell would also be zero, meaning every point on the phase space corresponds to a unique microstate (there are no limits on the accuracy of position and momentum measurements).

Let us now bring entropy into the picture. We have seen that entropy is positively correlated with the number of microstates. So, does it mean that if the number of microstates is infinite, entropy cannot increase any further? This argument seems to suggest that if the uncertainty principle was not true, entropy could not have increased with time in our universe. The second law of thermodynamics would not hold. Thus, from this we could argue that it is possible for entropy to increase in our universe because the uncertainty principle holds. This way, we may try to understand the increase in entropy (which is a macroscopic property) as a consequence of microscopic uncertainty. However, *this line of reasoning is not completely accurate*. Instead of concluding that entropy cannot increase when the number of microstates becomes infinite, it is more accurate to say that the notion

of counting microstates itself loses physical meaning in the classical limit where $h \rightarrow 0$. In classical mechanics, phase space is continuous, and every point corresponds to a distinct state. This leads formally to an uncountably infinite number of microstates even within a finite energy range. On the other hand, entropy in statistical mechanics is not defined by counting individual points in a continuum, but by introducing a physically meaningful *coarse-graining* of phase space.

The uncertainty principle provides precisely such a coarse-graining scale. By enforcing a minimum phase-space volume of order h^n , it allows us to partition phase space into finite-sized cells, each representing a distinguishable microstate. In this sense, quantum mechanics does not merely increase the number of accessible microstates, but rather makes the concept of microstate counting well-defined. Without this fundamental limit, entropy would depend on arbitrary choices of resolution and would not have a proper physical meaning.

Thus, instead of arguing that the uncertainty principle enables entropy to increase by preventing the number of microstates from becoming infinite, a more consistent interpretation is that it provides the necessary foundation for defining entropy itself. Once this minimal scale is introduced, changes in entropy can be understood as changes in the number of accessible coarse-grained microstates corresponding to a given macrostate. In this way, microscopic uncertainty does not directly drive entropy increase, but establishes the framework within which entropy and its evolution become physically meaningful.

One could perhaps go further and argue that Heisenberg's uncertainty principle provides the fundamental 'wiggle room' within which entropy can be meaningfully defined. Although quantum effects such as wave behavior become negligible at the macroscopic scale, the uncertainty principle continues to impose an intrinsic limit on how precisely position and momentum can be simultaneously specified at the microscopic level. In this sense, the uncertainty principle places a lower bound on the resolution of phase space, restricting how finely a microstate can be defined.

As we have seen, for macroscopic systems composed of a large number of microscopic particles, this limitation manifests as a natural coarse-graining of the phase space. Instead of associating microstates with exact points, we are compelled to associate them with finite regions consistent with the uncertainty principle. As a result, a single macrostate corresponds to a large number of distinguishable coarse-grained microstates, which forms the basis for the statistical definition of entropy. It is important to emphasize that entropy is not a measure of our lack of knowledge of the system (as in the information-theoretic

notion of entropy), but rather a measure of the number of physically accessible microstates compatible with a given macrostate.

At the same time, we must distinguish between microscopic uncertainty and macroscopic behavior. While individual particles are subject to fundamental uncertainty, interactions among a large number of particles and statistical averaging lead to stable and predictable macroscopic properties. This apparent reduction in uncertainty at the macroscopic level does not imply a reduction in entropy. On the contrary, it reflects the fact that many different microscopic configurations correspond to the same macroscopic description. Entropy arises precisely from this multiplicity of underlying microstates, not from the uncertainty of any individual particle.

Thus, rather than directly causing entropy to increase, the uncertainty principle provides the foundational framework that makes the notion of entropy physically meaningful by introducing a natural scale for distinguishing microstates. It ensures that the counting of microstates is not arbitrary, but grounded in fundamental physics. However, admittedly there is no compelling reason to claim that the uncertainty principle is responsible for the actual increase of entropy in our universe. To understand why entropy increases with time, we will now turn to a deeper and more fundamental concept: the arrow of time.

The Arrow of Time

A very important and fundamental idea that is often discussed alongside entropy is the arrow of time. It is a great puzzle that although the laws of physics make no distinction between the past and the future at the fundamental level – meaning it is theoretically possible for time to ‘run backward’ – yet we do not see a broken coffee mug pick itself up from the floor and repair itself. Why does time not run backward? We do not have a definitive answer yet, but the overall increase in the entropy of the universe is believed by many to be responsible for the unidirectional flow of time (often referred to as the arrow of time).

The Past, the Present and the Future

Time seems to be moving in one fixed direction: from the past to the future, much like an unstoppable river. It must be emphasized that the very nature of time is shrouded in mystery, and remains a hotly-debated topic today. All we know is that a notion of time is required to study the evolution of any system. But we do not understand time very well [16].

Time, according to some, is not a fundamental entity at all. Time (and space) could be emergent from a deeper level of reality. Some people think of time as the present moment; the past and future do not exist. More precisely, the past and future are uncertain. We have already discussed the double-slit experiment with electrons: When the electrons pass through both the slits and no measurement is made, we see an interference pattern on the final screen (electrons behave like waves); and if we put detectors before or after the slits, the electrons start behaving like particles, and the interference pattern is lost. In an experiment called the delayed choice quantum eraser experiment [17, 18], experimenters use light (photons) instead of electrons, and they can choose whether or not to attempt to determine which slit the photon came through *after* it has crossed the slit screen. It is seen that if we try to determine the slit the photon came through even after it has already passed through the slits, the interference pattern on the final screen is lost. Thus, essentially, the results of the double-slit experiment are true both into the future and past. A delayed choice on our end, like setting up detectors or not, seems to affect how light behaves in the past. This suggests that particles are connected (entangled) in time even when they are not connected in space.

Inspired partly by the results of the delayed choice experiment, John Wheeler put forward an intriguing idea, which he called “participatory universe theory”. According to Wheeler, the past and future are both undetermined, and in a way, we *participate* in the creation of the present, future as well as the past. To illustrate

this point, let us consider the negative twenty questions thought experiment. Suppose one is asked to think of some object (it could be anything). And the other is allowed to ask questions about this object, whose answers can be either yes or no. The questions could be: “Is it living?”, “Is it bigger than an elephant?” and so on. After asking a sufficiently large number of questions and analyzing the responses, it is possible to determine this object, much in the same way we discussed determining the contents in a message when discussing information. But here is the twist: Suppose in this experiment, when asked to think of any object, the subject does not think of anything in the first place, and keeps answering the questions posed randomly (or maybe according to some pattern, like yes-no-yes-no, or yes-yes-no-no). After a large number of questions, based on these random responses, both the experimenter and the subject would close in on a particular object, even though the subject did not think of anything initially. So, in some sense, the questions brought this object into existence in the minds of the experimenter and the subject. And the order of questioning is crucial. Suppose the subject decides to first answer yes and then no, and the first question is whether the object is living, and the second question is if it is big. Then the object could be an ant (since it is living and small). Of course, a conclusion cannot be formed without asking more questions, but an ant is a possibility. However, if the first question is whether the object is big, and the second question is if it is living, and the responses are still yes and then no, then the answer could be a house, which is big and not living, and very different from an ant. Now, it would be technically incorrect to say that the experimenter’s questions are affecting the past; the questions are only affecting what the subject thought of in the past, because the subject originally did not think of anything. However, this thought experiment is intended to highlight how the past is fundamentally uncertain, and can, in some sense, be created by our participation. Wheeler believed the reality we live in is the only reality which is consistent with our questioning. However, it must be emphasized that Wheeler’s idea is not widely accepted as a scientific interpretation of quantum mechanics, mainly due to its observer-dependency [19]. The idea has been briefly discussed here mainly because it beautifully illustrates why it is thought that both the past and the future could be uncertain. This gives rise to another puzzling question, however. If the past does not exist uniquely, how can we be sure it ever occurred in reality? What is preventing someone from rewriting history as they wish, as illustrated in the classic grandfather paradox?

In Newton’s days, it was generally believed that time was absolute. However, Einstein’s theory of relativity removes time from this pedestal of absoluteness, and places it as a relative parameter of his theory. Relativity proves that it is

possible for different observers in different reference frames to record the occurrence of the same event at different times. Einstein believed that we exist in a block universe: the past, present and future exist simultaneously, and the ‘flow of time’ is an illusion. Of course we perceive the flow of time. But time is just a fourth dimension in Einstein’s theory, which together with the three spatial dimensions, forms what we call spacetime. This spacetime, as a whole, is not changing. The illusion of the ‘flow of time’ is a consequence of us moving through this fixed spacetime. This, however, is only an interpretation of time based on relativity, and not everyone agrees with this interpretation.

We discussed some ideas about the nature of time; however, we are mainly interested in studying the unidirectional flow of time. The questions of whether time really ‘flows’ or whether time is emergent and not fundamental are extremely deep and interesting questions, but we will not discuss these questions in this report. Our main concern is that most of the equations of physics treat time as symmetric. Much of physics would be theoretically valid even if time ran backward. Then, why does time move only forward (from the past to the future) in our universe? Why do we not see a broken coffee mug pick itself up from the floor and repair itself? The most widely accepted view is that time does not flow backward because entropy must always increase in our universe, according to the second law of thermodynamics. This requires unidirectional flow of time. The arrow of time is, thus, believed to be a consequence of the second law of thermodynamics.

The Three Arrows of Time

We can define three different arrows of time: the thermodynamic arrow of time, the psychological arrow of time and the cosmological arrow of time [20]. The thermodynamic arrow of time is the arrow of time that arises due to entropy increasing in our universe. The unidirectional nature of the second law of thermodynamics is apparent from the fact that the overall entropy of the universe can only increase and not decrease. Thus, we can think of the increase in entropy as an arrow of time; time is only allowed to ‘flow’ in the direction of increasing entropy, because entropy can only increase over time. The psychological arrow of time is a consequence of the thermodynamic arrow, and both these arrows of time always point in the same direction. The psychological arrow of time simply refers to our subjective experience of the unidirectional flow of time from the past to the future; we can form memories of the past but not the future. When a brain or a computer forms a memory, it becomes more ordered. This is because a memory of a particular event contains information about that event, and

information can be correlated with reduction in uncertainty or randomness associated with the event. A memory is a highly-organized and fixed pattern of neuronal connections in the brain, which is a low entropy state as compared to the more random state before the memory was formed. However, to form a memory, a brain (or a computer) needs to do significant work and release heat into the surroundings, thus contributing to the overall increase in the entropy of the universe. This illustrates the connection between the thermodynamic and psychological arrows of time.

The cosmological arrow of time relates to the expansion of the universe. This arrow points in the direction of the expanding universe, because observations have verified that the universe expands (and does not contract) over time, from the past to the future. Einstein's theory of general relativity allows for both contracting and expanding solutions, meaning a contracting universe is a theoretical possibility in general relativity. We do not exactly know why the universe expands, while it could have contracted, in which case the cosmological arrow of time would have pointed in the opposite direction. The cosmological arrow of time changing direction does not, of course, mean that the thermodynamic and psychological arrows also change direction. As we have discussed previously, entropy could increase even in a contracting universe. The cosmological arrow of time is not fully understood; it is believed that a more complete understanding of the initial conditions of the universe would shed more light on this. That requires a theory that can deal with the conditions prevalent in the very early universe: extremely small length scales (which requires quantum mechanics) and extremely high energies (which requires general relativity). Unfortunately, we do not have such a theory yet.

An answer to the question of why the three arrows of time all point in the same direction is that otherwise, intelligent life could not have formed and evolved in the universe. To start with, life breaks down ordered forms of energy (like food) into more disordered forms, and dissipates heat and increases the disorder in its surroundings to stay alive. Thus, the thermodynamic arrow of time must point in the direction of increasing entropy for intelligent life to exist in the universe. Further, for life to evolve, lifeforms must be able to process information around them, form memories and also be able to use these memories to guide future actions and decisions. In a universe where the three arrows of time were not aligned in the same direction, life would not be able to evolve. Simply put, we would not be here asking why the three arrows of time point in the same direction if they did not. We know that the thermodynamic and psychological arrows of time always point in the same direction. If the cosmological arrow of time were to point in the opposite direction, it would mean the universe contracts over time,

which is not conducive to the emergence and existence of intelligent life. As the universe contracts, the average distance between any two objects in the universe decreases, thus accelerating the effect of gravitational pull, and hence accelerating the contraction of the universe. Further, temperatures would go up, making things even more difficult for life. However, the above argument only shows why the existence of life requires all the three arrows of time to point in the same direction; it cannot be considered a complete explanation of why the three arrows of time do, in fact, point in the same direction in our universe.

Entropy and the Cosmological Arrow of Time

As we have discussed, it is widely believed that entropy gives rise to the arrow of time (more appropriately, the thermodynamic arrow of time). However, we argue that it is possible that the cosmological arrow of time is responsible for the increase in entropy in our universe and gives rise to the thermodynamic arrow of time. Let us discuss the reasoning behind this argument. We have previously discussed how the uncertainty principle in quantum mechanics might provide room for entropy to increase in our universe. This means the increase in entropy (or the thermodynamic arrow of time) owes its origins to quantum uncertainty; and there is no arrow of time in quantum mechanics, time symmetry is not broken in quantum mechanics. This seems to indicate that entropy does not arise because of the arrow of time, since the uncertainty principle does not talk about any arrow of time. One might be tempted to conclude that the arrow of time is a consequence of the second law of thermodynamics.

However, here we argue that the cosmological arrow of time is the most fundamental. The thermodynamic arrow of time could be a consequence of increasing entropy, but we assume the cosmological arrow of time to be responsible for increasing entropy and the thermodynamic arrow of time. Let us try to construct an argument, although not a very rigorous one, in favor of this assumption. Assuming the cosmological arrow of time to be fundamental, we essentially fix the direction of time at the very beginning of the universe. This limits the number of possible ways we can perform a time measurement. Since the universe expands into the future, the cosmological arrow of time points in the direction from the past and toward the future. This means we cannot measure time from the future. In a way, this reduces the number of possible time measurements, and hence the uncertainty in time. According to Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, this must result in an increase in uncertainty in energy measurements, and hence an increase in the number of possible energy measurements.

The entropy of a system is measured at a particular instant in time. Hence, constraining the number of possible time measurements has no effect on the entropy of the universe at any given time. On the other hand, more freedom in energy measurements indicates a higher number of possible energy measurements, and hence a higher entropy. As the universe evolves in the direction of the arrow of time, more and more time measurements in the past (time measurements that correspond to a lower overall entropy) become impossible. For instance, if we perform a time measurement now, in agreement with the present overall entropy of the universe, we cannot obtain a value that corresponds to a time in the past, when the overall entropy of the universe was lower. As the universe keeps expanding, more and more time measurement outcomes become impossible, and more and more energy measurement outcomes become possible, and the overall entropy keeps increasing until the end of time, when everything in the universe is in perfect thermal equilibrium with one another and the universe reaches a maximum entropy state.

A serious flaw in the above argument is that in the uncertainty principle, we talk about measurements of an *interval* of time, and not a fixed point in time. So, should it really matter if one measures a time interval of five seconds now or a million years ago into the past? A possible answer to this question could be given by employing the same argument above in reverse: Depending on the overall entropy of the universe, the number of allowed energy microstates in the system will vary, and this will affect the uncertainty in energy measurements, and hence the uncertainty in time measurements. Essentially, we assume the universe to be evolving from a state of extremely low entropy to a state of maximum entropy, and throughout this journey, there is a one-to-one correspondence between entropy and time. In other words, we can uniquely assign a particular 'time' to every state of the universe (between the initial and final states); and every unique state of the universe has a particular value of overall entropy. Time, here, does not simply play the role of keeping a record of the evolution for universe, it is inextricably linked to the overall entropy of the universe. The next objection to this argument is obvious: When we talk about the uncertainty principle, we talk about individual, microscopic particles; when we talk about entropy, however, we talk about macroscopic systems made of a large number of microscopic particles. However, if we accept that quantum uncertainty has a role to play in the emergence of macroscopic entropy, it could be possible that the macroscopic entropy of a system exercises some influence over the microscopic uncertainty in that system. In theory, the uncertainty principle holds for large objects just as well as it does for microscopic particles, although the effect is much less noticeable in large objects.

We must acknowledge that unlike the previous argument that links entropy to the uncertainty principle, the above argument about entropy and the arrow of time is based on a lot of assumptions, most of which have not been rigorously explained. Thus, the above idea cannot, in its present form, be put forward as a proper scientific hypothesis. However, a primary motivation behind assuming the cosmological arrow of time to be more fundamental than entropy is that it is difficult to properly define entropy for a perfectly ordered and extreme state like the initial state of the universe (the Big Bang state, basically a huge concentration of energy packed in an infinitesimally small region of space). The cosmological arrow of time came into play as soon as the universe came into existence, and the expansion of the universe was initiated. Entropy and the thermodynamic arrow of time come into the picture slightly later. As the universe began to expand, it possibly went through an inflationary period which smoothed out irregularities to an extent that is allowed by the uncertainty principle. After that, the expansion began to slow down locally and matter clumped together to form galaxies, stars and eventually us. Clearly, a universe filled with stars, galaxies and complex lifeforms like us is much more disordered than a universe without such structures. Thus, disorder in the universe increased, bringing the thermodynamic arrow of time into the picture.

It is, of course, not clearly understood why exactly the universe began to expand in the first place. It is believed that a definitive answer can only be given by a unified theory that is more fundamental than anything we have seen so far. The expansion of the universe could likely be attributed to the very specific initial conditions, although we cannot explain these initial conditions using present knowledge. It seems that there probably was some time asymmetry inherent in the initial state of the universe, which was responsible for the cosmological arrow of time (the unidirectional nature of time) and the expansion of the universe. In this view, we claim time (and the cosmological arrow of time) to be more fundamental than entropy (and the thermodynamic arrow of time) because time came into play as soon as the universe came into existence, but entropy probably came into the picture slightly later, when we could meaningfully measure the disorder in the universe.

The general theory of relativity might hold a clue about explaining the origins of the cosmological arrow of time. General relativity treats time as a fourth dimension, but mathematically in a way that is not entirely similar to the treatment of the three spatial dimensions. In an expanding universe, the structure of spacetime as described by general relativity would favor time flowing from the past to the future, as we observe, and not the other way round. However, of course, this does not answer why the universe started to expand in the first place. There

have been attempts to explain this by putting forward the idea of the existence of a parallel, contracting universe. It has been proposed that the Big Bang gave rise to two universes with two cosmological arrows of time pointing in opposite directions, and we find ourselves in the universe where the cosmological arrow of time is aligned with the thermodynamic and psychological arrows of time, which is necessary for intelligent lifeforms to emerge and evolve. A study by Julian Barbour and others [21] suggests that gravity is responsible for the direction of the arrow of time. It is usually believed that the universe began in an extremely low entropy state; this helps explain why entropy increases over time in our universe. However, Barbour and his group used computer simulations to study the evolution of a simple model of the universe under the influence of Newtonian gravity. They found that in their model, regardless of the initial conditions, gravity is able to collapse the system into a dense, ordered state, which then starts expanding. We may interpret this ordered state to be a unique past, from which two parallel universes were then observed to emerge and evolve in two separate directions, each with its own arrow of time. And in both these universes, over time there were local dips in entropy and particles clumped together to form structures that can be held equivalent to stars and galaxies in the physical universe. Essentially, two futures (two parallel universes) emerge from a unique past (the state of lowest complexity).

Figure 11: A simple system of point particles under the influence of Newtonian gravity, collapses into a compact, low-complexity state. We may interpret this state as a unique past, from which two futures, with their arrows of time pointing in opposite directions, emerge. (Source: Alan Stonebraker, American Physical Society.)

The strength of this idea is that it does not assume very specific initial conditions of the universe to explain the arrow of time, instead it tries to explain how the state of lowest complexity might be a result of simple physical laws like Isaac

Newton's law of gravity. And from this state, two parallel universes emerge, with two distinct arrows of time. Entropy increases in both these universes, and both these universes could possibly support intelligent life. However, all of these conclusions are based on an extremely simplified model which does not take into account the effects of general relativity and quantum fluctuations in the early universe. Thus, while the results are undoubtedly interesting, we do not know if this actually applies to our universe.

Something similar is observed in open quantum systems. The reason open quantum systems are considered is that they interact with their surroundings; and hence we can meaningfully study the flow of time in such systems. A study by Andrea Rocco and others [22] found that time symmetry is not broken by open quantum systems; and entropy increases both into the past as well as into the future. This does not mean we get to see a broken coffee mug repair itself; rather if we consider entropy increasing in the past, the coffee mug still breaks but the clock ticks backward. This means it is not possible to distinguish the past from the future, and entropy increasing in the past is equally likely as entropy increasing in the future for open quantum systems. This study only shows that mathematically both are equally possible, but once the arrow of time physically chooses a particular direction, it is stuck in that direction, and cannot reverse its direction midway since entropy will keep increasing in that direction. We do not know how or why the arrow of time in our universe chose the direction that we observe. A speculative answer could, again, be framed using the familiar idea of the Big Bang giving rise to two parallel universes with two opposite arrows of time.

To sum up, as we have discussed previously, quantum uncertainty provides some room for entropy to increase. Quantum uncertainty does not necessarily cause entropy to increase, but creates a universe in which it is possible for entropy to increase. And then in this section, we have argued that the cosmological arrow of time and the initial conditions of the early universe are driving the increase in entropy in the universe, and are thus responsible for the thermodynamic arrow of time. The cosmological arrow of time and initial conditions of the universe are not well understood, and there have been speculations that there is a parallel universe, in addition to our own, in which the cosmological arrow of time points in a different direction. Some studies seem to suggest entropy can increase both into the past and into the future, inspiring the idea that two futures can emerge from a common past.

Ergodicity and the Postulate of Equal A Priori Probabilities

A fundamental assumption in statistical mechanics is that every possible microstate is equally likely for a system in equilibrium. Fundamentally, we cannot assume a particular microstate to be more probable than any other microstate without precisely explaining this preference. We do not expect to see any particular possibility being preferred over any other possibility at a fundamental level. Consider our discussion on the cosmological arrow of time. It is possible for it to point both into the future and into the past, but observations confirm that in our universe, it points into the future. To get around this ‘preference,’ the idea of a parallel universe where the cosmological arrow of time points in the opposite direction has been considered. Essentially, we feel every possibility must occur in reality somewhere at some point in time. This is beautifully captured in the popular saying: “Everything not forbidden is compulsory” [23].

In statistical mechanics, we have two extremely fundamental ideas that we will now briefly discuss: ergodicity and the postulate of equal a priori probabilities [24]. The relevance of this discussion will become apparent when we discuss Boltzmann’s ideas about the universe having a very unlikely initial state. Let us begin with ergodicity. According to the ergodic hypothesis in statistical mechanics, the time average of a macroscopic parameter of a system in equilibrium must be equal to the ensemble average of the same parameter of the same system in equilibrium. Suppose we want to measure a macroscopic parameter A of a box of gas in equilibrium with its surroundings. Let us construct a hypothetical scenario in which we measure A for this system a very large number of times, and at infinitesimal intervals of time. Then we calculate the average of all these values. This is the time average of the parameter A . Next, let us consider another hypothetical picture in which we create a very large number of identical copies (an ensemble) of this system in space. When we say “identical copies,” we mean all these copies must be in the same macrostate. As we have already discussed, there can be many possible microstates corresponding to the same macrostate; thus all these identical copies of our system are allowed to be in different microstates, as long as they correspond to the same macrostate. Now, imagine we measure the parameter A of all these copies of the system at once, and calculate the average of all the obtained values; this gives the ensemble average of A for this system. According to the ergodic hypothesis, both these average values (the time average and the ensemble average) should be equal. One might wonder what is the need of even considering the ensemble average, since we have said that all the “identical copies” have the same macrostate, and we are measuring a macroscopic parameter A . Should all these “identical copies” not have the same value of A ? It is important to realize that certain macroscopic

parameters of a system are functions of the underlying microstate, and can vary across microstates corresponding to a macrostate that is defined using some other macroscopic parameter. Ensemble-averaging becomes important when we are measuring such a parameter. For example, say we have a box of gas where the energy is fixed. There are many possible microstates corresponding to this same energy macrostate. We, however, are interested in measuring the pressure. The pressure of this system will be different for these different microstates, even though all of them correspond to the same energy. In some microstates, the particles will be colliding with the walls of the box more frequently; in some other microstates, the particles will be colliding among themselves in the middle of the box more frequently, and so on. The pressure would be different for each microstate, and the average pressure can be determined by averaging the pressure measurement outcomes obtained for each microstate (ensemble average).

Let us now think about the implications of the apparently obvious-sounding claim that the time and ensemble averages must be equal. When we consider the identical copies (ensemble) of the system, we take into account all the possible, unique microstates of the system. And this number is very large, infinite for all practical purposes. Imagine all the possible combinations of position and momenta of all the microscopic gas molecules in a box of gas made of a large number of molecules; this is a huge number. This means, in the ensemble, we have one copy of each microstate corresponding to the given macrostate. The ensemble average, thus, is the average of all the values obtained for each microstate, counted only once. And when we are making a large (infinite) number of measurements at very small intervals of time to calculate the time average, we get the same result. This means as the system evolves over a sufficiently long period of time, it accesses all the possible, unique microstates (that correspond to the given macrostate). And importantly, the system will never revisit a microstate it has already visited without first covering all the available microstates. Consider the number of microstates to be infinite, this implies that it is equally likely to find a system in equilibrium in any one of the possible microstates that correspond to the given macrostate. This, in fact, is the postulate of equal a priori probability, which implicitly assumes ergodicity.

Let us now recall that the phase trajectory of the evolving system is obtained by joining the phase points at successive intervals of time. Based on the ideas discussed above, we see that the phase trajectory of a system in equilibrium cannot intersect itself. That would mean the system revisits the same microstate more than once, implying that particular microstate is more likely than the other microstates, in contradiction with the postulate of equal a priori probabilities. Of course, intersection is not allowed also because at the point of intersection, the

system could be in more than one microstate simultaneously, which does not make sense. This is somewhat similar to why electric field lines cannot intersect, because then we would have two possible directions of the electric field at the point of intersection.

Essentially, the phase trajectory will tend to move through the entire available volume of the phase space (all the available microstates) without intersecting itself. This is somewhat similar, in essence, to a self-avoiding walk. A self-avoiding walk is the path traced out by a sequence of moves through points on a lattice, such that one point is not visited more than once.

Figure 12: A self-avoiding walk. (Source: Wikipedia.)

Simply put, if we have ten single rooms in a guest house and nine guests, we would allocate nine unique rooms to the guests, and certainly not force two of them into the same room. In the same way, if we imagine each point in the above figure to represent a microstate, the system will not revisit a point it has already visited before exploring the other unexplored options. We observe similar behavior in rivers too, even though a real river does not flow through a phase space. A river flows in a path that never comes back and intersects itself. If it encounters an obstacle (like a cliff), it bifurcates and sometimes rejoins, finds a new path and keeps flowing, but never turns back and forms a loop. Although local vortices and eddies form in a river, the overall flow of a river is unidirectional, and this is why the arrow of time is often compared to the flow of a river. Time cannot form a loop and revisit a point in the past; otherwise science

fiction tales involving time machines would not be half as interesting and intriguing!

The above discussion, however, leaves us with a puzzling insight. According to the postulate of equal a priori probabilities, all the microstates corresponding to a given macrostate of a system in equilibrium are equally probable. Let us consider a box of ideal gas. It is perfectly possible that two different configurations of the gas particles – say one in which they are huddled close together in a corner of the box, and another in which they move through the entire volume of the box – correspond to the same temperature of the system. These two configurations, shown in the figure below, are two possible microstates corresponding to the same macrostate (temperature).

Figure 13: Two configurations of gas particles in a box of ideal gas. (Created using GasLab NetLogo.)

The pressure of the gas and occupied volume varies in the two cases, but that does not necessarily affect the temperature of the system, as long as the average kinetic energy of the gas particles remains the same.

Now, according to the postulate of equal a priori probabilities, both the above configurations (which correspond to two possible microstates corresponding to the given temperature) are equally likely. However, from our knowledge of entropy, it appears that the configuration in which the particles are huddled in a corner (say, configuration A) is a low entropy configuration, and should be less likely as compared to the other configuration (say, configuration B) in a universe where the entropy of a closed system cannot decrease (assume this box of gas to be a closed system, it does not interact with its surroundings). This means if we

find the system in configuration B (assuming the system has not yet been in the configuration A), we would expect not to find the system in configuration A ever. In a universe where the entropy of a closed system cannot decrease, how can we expect gas particles in a spread-out configuration to spontaneously collapse together in a small region of space, which is clearly a low entropy configuration? However, the postulate of equal a priori probabilities demands that even this ‘unlikely’ configuration be attained by the system, since it is equally likely as the other configurations as long as they correspond to the given macrostate.

Clearly, in configuration A, the volume available to the gas particles is limited, reducing the number of spatial configurations. Now, since entropy depends not just on the number of possible spatial configurations, but also energy and velocity configurations, one might argue that when the gas molecules are close together, due to interaction the number of velocity and energy configurations increase, thus making up for the decrease in the number of possible spatial configurations and ensuring entropy does not decrease. However, this argument is flawed because we are talking about a system of ideal gas. Ideal gas particles do not have potential energy, and the kinetic energies of ideal gas particles (and hence their velocities) depend solely on the temperature. At a constant temperature (which is the given macrostate here), the energies and velocities of the particles would remain unaffected regardless of whether the particles are spread out or huddled in a corner. This means that configuration A certainly has a lower entropy than configuration B. There is only one conclusion: if we wait long enough, it is indeed possible that a system transitions, all by itself, from a high entropy configuration to a low entropy configuration. This can be thought of as a result of an extremely improbable (but not impossible) statistical fluctuation. Of course, this can be ignored for all practical purposes, and this conclusion cannot be drawn from the second law of thermodynamics, which simply states that the entropy of a closed system is not allowed to decrease. And yes, this law is correct, but it is a statistical law. It works extremely well in all cases practically. However, theoretically, we cannot ignore this strange conclusion that even in a closed system, a spontaneous transition from to a lower entropy state could be possible.

A Very Unlikely Initial State

In light of the above discussions, it is clear that we do not fundamentally understand why entropy increases in our universe. To answer this question, Boltzmann assumed that our universe began in a very unlikely, low entropy state [25]. This assumption is referred to as the past hypothesis, but the problem with the idea is that it is a postulate that cannot be questioned and if questioned, it

cannot generate any further insights about the subject. It almost feels like sweeping the real question under the rug by forcefully postulating that the universe began in a low entropy state.

Based on current knowledge, it is believed that the universe formed from the Big Bang state – a single, tiny, infinitely dense and huge concentration of energy. It is speculated that this state was the result of a quantum fluctuation in vacuum (empty space). The uncertainty principle in quantum mechanics leaves room for fluctuations in vacuum energy, and leaves open the possibility of the emergence of a state like the Big Bang. However, we do not have a complete understanding of the Big Bang. In its present form, the Big Bang theory only explains certain aspects of the evolution of the universe, but not its origins.

As we have discussed, the equations of general relativity allow for both expanding and contracting universes. At that time, it was believed that the universe was static. Respecting this belief, Einstein introduced a cosmological constant to his equations ‘to keep the universe static.’ But then it was discovered (rather accidentally) that everything in the universe is actually accelerating away in all directions. This means galaxies are moving away from one another, and as the distances between them keep on increasing, the effect of gravitational attraction decreases rapidly, meaning the galaxies move away even faster. This means in the past, everything in the universe was closer together, until the beginning of time, when it was all essentially a single point – the Big Bang. It is believed that the Big Bang started expanding, and initially underwent a period of inflation (accelerated expansion) which played an important role in ensuring the smoothness of the early universe. With its expansion, the universe cooled down, and fundamental particles and atoms were formed. Eventually, in certain regions, the expansion of the universe slowed down locally, and clusters were formed due to gravitational pull. Gravity confined huge, rotating clouds of gases to sufficiently small regions such that the internuclear distances were small enough to support nuclear fusion reactions. This is how stars were formed and they eventually spat out clumps of matter that became the planets, which began orbiting the stars.

Throughout the process, the entropy of the universe has been on an increase; formation of galaxies, stars and even intelligent life greatly increased the complexity and disorder in the universe, and the number of possible spatial configurations of matter in the universe also increased due to the expansion of the universe and more volume becoming available to the matter in the universe (indicating an increase in the number of microstates).

Figure 14: Timeline of the evolution of the universe. (Source: Wikipedia.)

It is known that in the early universe, density of matter was much higher than it is today, and the gravitational pull between particles was extremely strong. It is also known, based on evidence like the Cosmic Microwave Background radiation, that the early universe was very smooth and homogeneous. We are talking about a time when matter had not clustered into structures like stars and galaxies, and the matter density and overall temperature of the universe was almost constant. This smoothness of the early universe is perplexing [26]. The universe must have been perfectly smooth, because even slight imperfections or non-uniformity in the density of matter would have caused the universe to collapse under the strong influence of gravity. This points at very special initial conditions of the universe. Only a small number of precise configurations would be able to maintain this overall smoothness. Clearly, this means the early universe was in a state of extremely low entropy, since there were very few ways one could prepare this state. Since the universe started off in a state of extremely low entropy, it is more likely for the overall entropy of the universe to increase rather than decrease further. This, however, is a probabilistic statement. Recall from our discussion on the postulate of equal a priori probabilities that all possible microscopic configurations for a given macrostate of a system in equilibrium (assume the universe is an isolated, closed system) are equally likely. Thus, in theory, if we wait long enough, we would watch configurations that seem unlikely, like the smooth configuration of the early universe. We have already discussed the essence of this argument previously. It is possible for gas particles in a system of ideal gas, initially in a spread-out configuration, to spontaneously come close together and huddle in a corner, simply because both these

configurations can correspond to the same temperature (same macrostate) of the system, and are equally likely according to the postulate of equal a priori probabilities.

Let us consider such a spontaneous transition from a high entropy state to a low entropy state in a system, due to a random statistical fluctuation. Such transitions are never observed in the real world because they are very, *very* unlikely, and virtually impossible within time periods that we can analyze. But theoretically, the probability of such a transition is not zero.

Let us now picture a box of ideal gas, initially in configuration A where the gas particles are relatively spread out as they move about randomly. Then, all of a sudden, the particles collapse into a corner of the box, all by themselves (configuration B). Then the particles spread out again (configuration C). Clearly, configuration B has the lowest entropy, the previous configuration A as well as the subsequent configuration C have higher entropies than configuration B. This illustrates how entropy can increase both into the past as well as in the future.

Figure 15: Entropy can increase both into the past as well as into the future. Note that there can be entropy fluctuations due to microscopic randomness, but the overall change in entropy as a function of time is shown by the dark black U-shaped curve. (Source: arXiv. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1809.04646>)

In the same way, we could start with a high entropy configuration, and arrive at a low entropy configuration like the Big Bang state via a random statistical fluctuation. Then again entropy begins to increase as the Big Bang state starts to expand. Over a long period of time, it is expected that the universe would reach a state of maximum entropy, when everything in the universe would be in perfect equilibrium with everything else. Of course, life would no longer exist in such a

state, because intelligent life must be able to perceive changes around them, perceive the passage of time, process information, form memories, metabolize and so on. No change could occur in the maximum entropy state, since it is already in perfect equilibrium, and any flow of energy or information between its parts would mean disrupting that equilibrium. Entropy could no longer increase since it has already attained its maximum value, and the arrow of time would vanish.

The above plot of entropy as a function of time (Figure 15) shows entropy increasing both into the past and the future. Boltzmann hypothesized that over a very long period of time, statistical fluctuations could give rise to both small as well as big dips in entropy [27]. Clearly, our place in this picture is a point on the entropy-vs-time curve with a positive slope (Figure 16). This indicates that the entropy is increasing right now, since we started off in a very unusual state, which was probably the result of a statistical fluctuation from a more probable earlier state.

Figure 16: Our universe might owe its origins to a low entropy fluctuation in a bigger universe at a higher entropy state, and we could exist somewhere in the upward slope as entropy increases with the evolution of the universe. (Source: arXiv. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1809.04646>)

This line of argument leads us to even more bizarre possibilities. In an infinitely big universe, over a sufficiently long period of time, there could be bigger fluctuations into lower entropy states. Cosmology tells us that the universe came into existence about 13.8 billion years ago, and eventually evolved to its present form, where we find ourselves in. Statistically however, it is more probable for the fluctuation to simply create a single conscious brain, complete with false memories of a past that never really occurred, rather than creating a state like the Big Bang and eventually a real universe with all this complexity! This absurd-

sounding idea is often referred to as the Boltzmann brain hypothesis. From a purely statistical point of view, this argument makes sense. It is more probable, for instance, for some particles to spontaneously come together and arrange themselves in precisely the right way to create a smartphone, than for some particles to come together in precisely the way required for a universe to form, that would then evolve in exactly the way necessary for intelligent life to emerge, and eventually the lifeforms would evolve into creatures sufficiently intelligent to manufacture a smartphone. Of course, we would never expect to see a smartphone assemble all by itself; this event is so unlikely that it is impossible from a practical perspective. However, statistically it is still more probable than the other option. In the same way, is it not more likely that a single brain spontaneously self-assembles with false memories of the past, rather than the entire universe – with all its structures – spontaneously emerging? If we think about the Big Bang state, it is improbable, but not impossible, that all the particles in a high entropy universe suddenly collapse to the low entropy Big Bang configuration. The point is, although theory leaves out some possibility, however small, for all the particles to end up at a single, extremely dense point, smaller, localized dips in entropy are much more likely. So why collapse an entire universe instead of assembling a random collection of particles into a single brain?

This absurd hypothesis is, undoubtedly, intriguing. However, many flaws with this argument have been identified [27]. Feynman pointed out that if the world around us was the result of a random fluctuation, we would not have found that the predictions we make based on observations on our immediate surroundings hold consistently in a distant part of the world, or the universe. For example, Newton's law of gravity holds just as good for a stone thrown upwards from Earth as it does for the Earth and the Sun, and it does so always. It is not that we find Newton's law worked yesterday but does not work today. Similarly, we do not see different results if we perform a scientific experiment today or tomorrow, provided we keep the external conditions exactly the same on both days. Feynman argued that we would have observed major inconsistencies around us if the world did not exist physically and was just the result of a random fluctuation. Sean Carroll puts forward another powerful counterargument. If we accept that the Boltzmann brain hypothesis is true, we essentially accept that the world around us is not real, but simulated. However, we were led to form this hypothesis based on observations on this simulated world. If this world is not real, these observations, and hence the hypothesis, cannot be trusted. Essentially, Carroll argues that if we accept that we are Boltzmann brains, we cannot trust any of our thoughts since Boltzmann brains result from random fluctuations and are "cognitively unstable" [28].

So, if the world is not a fluctuation, why was the early universe in such an extremely unlikely, low entropy state? We do not have a definitive answer today, and it is possible we never will. This could simply be a brute fact, an unknowable feature of the universe that cannot be understood in terms of anything more fundamental. We just have to accept it as a postulate. Boltzmann realized that it could be possible that the unlikely initial state of the universe cannot be explained, and has to be accepted as a fact. He said [29]: “That in nature the transition from a probable to an improbable state does not take place as often as the converse, can be explained by assuming a very improbable initial state of the entire universe surrounding us. This is a reasonable assumption to make, since it enables us to explain the facts of experience, and one should not expect to be able to deduce it from anything more fundamental.”

There is an alternative way to approach this problem. We may discard the assumption that the universe is a closed and isolated system, and that the Big Bang was the beginning of it all [26]. Our universe could be part of a bigger universe; in which smaller universes endlessly form and collapse. These ideas are not simply figments of imagination, we have indirect evidence suggesting that such a picture is possible, at least in theory. The idea of parallel universes crops up in inflation theory in cosmology, the many-worlds interpretation in quantum mechanics etc. Although parallel realities in many-worlds interpretation are not exactly identical to the parallel universes that are seen in inflationary cosmology, the idea of parallel universes seems to have stuck with physicists.

It is believed that fundamentally, every possibility must take place. It might appear crude to simply hypothesize that the possibilities that do not occur in our universe might occur in parallel universes, but the idea of parallel universes has its strengths and appeal. Max Tegmark makes a beautiful point that shows why the idea of parallel universes might not be as preposterous as it sounds [30]: “If you’re... struggling to make inner peace with parallel universes, here’s another way of thinking about them that might help... When we discover an object in Nature, the scientific thing to do is look for a mechanism that created it. Cars are created by car factories, rabbits are created by rabbit parents and solar systems are created from gravitational collapse in giant molecular clouds. So it’s quite reasonable to assume that our universe was created by some sort of universe-creation mechanism... Now here’s the thing: all the other mechanisms we mentioned naturally produce many copies of whatever they create; a cosmos containing only one car, one rabbit, and one solar system would seem quite contrived. In the same vein, it’s arguably more natural for the correct universe-creation mechanism, whatever it is, to create many universes rather than just the one we inhabit.”

Of course, these ideas are of little practical importance and remain out of reach of experimental falsification and are largely speculative. However, these arguments, counterarguments and ideas are so deep and fascinating that engaging in them not only offers great intellectual stimulation, but can also potentially offer insights about the fundamental nature of the universe.

Conclusion

This report explores the intersection of three major branches of physics: quantum mechanics, statistical mechanics and cosmology. We first discuss the uncertainty principle in quantum mechanics, which fundamentally limits the accuracy with which we can determine the state of a particle. The uncertainty principle has been explored in depth, with the help of relevant thought experiments like the double-slit experiment with electrons, and a modified version of the same experiment used by Feynman to better illustrate the consequences of the uncertainty principle. Then we discuss entropy, both qualitatively and quantitatively from a statistical mechanics perspective. The idea of information is then introduced, with special emphasis on its role in quantum mechanics and statistical mechanics. The quantum postulate of unitarity implies time symmetry is respected in quantum mechanics and shows that information must be preserved in the evolution of any quantum system. On the other hand, there is a strong connection between entropy and information, which we explore with the help of relevant concepts like Shannon's entropy.

Next, we explore the possibility that the increase in the entropy of closed systems, as dictated by the second law of thermodynamics, is a consequence of microscopic uncertainty, as dictated by the uncertainty principle in quantum mechanics. Before exploring this idea, relevant concepts in statistical mechanics – phase space, macrostates, microstates, phase cells, density of states – have been introduced. Then we attempt to combine the facts that the uncertainty principle does not allow us to perfectly determine the microstate of a system, and entropy increases when the number of possible microstates of the system increases, and based on this, we try to understand macroscopic entropy as a consequence of microscopic uncertainty.

In the final chapter of the report, we explore the connection between entropy and the arrow of time. First, we discuss some popular views on the nature of time, exploring relevant thought experiments, like the delayed choice quantum eraser, wherever needed. Next, we turn to the three arrows of time: the cosmological arrow of time, the thermodynamic arrow of time and the psychological arrow of time. We explore both how these arrows differ from one another and how they are related to one another. Next, we ask whether arrow of time is a result of the second law of thermodynamics or the other way round. The standard view holds that the increase in entropy is responsible for the unidirectional nature of time. However, we explore the alternatives and put forward an argument that the cosmological arrow of time is responsible for the increase in entropy and the

thermodynamic arrow of time. We clearly highlight some potential flaws with our argument as well. We also discuss why the cosmological arrow of time points in the direction it does, and look at an interesting study that predicts the existence of a parallel universe with a cosmological arrow of time pointing in the opposite direction. Next, we introduce some fundamental ideas in statistical mechanics, namely the ergodic hypothesis and the postulate of equal a priori probabilities, and explain why the second law of thermodynamics is a statistical law. Based on this, we discuss the past hypothesis, which claims that the universe began in a very unlikely, low entropy state. We finally explore the possibility that the world around us could be nothing more than a random, low entropy fluctuation from a state with a higher entropy, and some intriguing ideas that follow from this, like the Boltzmann brain.

We have primarily tried to explore the connection between quantum uncertainty, statistical entropy and the arrow of time in this report. In addition, we have introduced many fundamental concepts across quantum mechanics and statistical mechanics in significant depth and accessible language. Our argument can be briefly summed up as follows: The second law of thermodynamics could be a consequence of the cosmological arrow of time; and while quantum uncertainty might not be directly responsible for driving the increase in entropy, it provides the foundational framework that allows entropy to be defined and to evolve meaningfully in our universe, and may therefore be viewed as a necessary condition for the second law of thermodynamics to operate.

Appendix A: Energy, Entropy and Symmetry

When we think of the universe, we are often reminded of a cold, dark and desolate stretch of spacetime, with tiny dots (galaxies) and even tinier dots (stars) trying their best to scream out their existence to the surrounding void. This picture might paint a universe that is devoid of much activity. However, a large portion of the matter in the universe is not in equilibrium. If everything in the universe was in a state of perfect equilibrium, we would not exist in the first place. In fact, out of the many possible fates of the universe, one holds that over a long period of time, every part of the universe would reach a state of thermal equilibrium with every other part, meaning there would be no difference in temperature and energy between the different parts of the universe that could cause some changes to occur.

In their quest to understand the perplexities of the universe at all length scales, physicists have tried to identify and quantify potential fundamental parameters in terms of which a wide range of physical phenomena can be studied. Perhaps the two most important parameters in this regard are energy and entropy. Energy is that quantity which is usually minimized with time, as different processes evolve. An open system, which can interact with its surroundings, usually tends to lose energy to its surroundings over time, and minimize its own energy. For closed systems, with time the energy usually spreads out uniformly throughout the system. Everything in the universe, broadly speaking, tends to reach an equilibrium state, a state of minimum energy or a state in which the energy is evenly distributed in the entire system, depending on whether the system is open or closed. This simple idea can explain a lot of changes we see in the world around us. Studying the world through the lens of energy has proved to be a time-tested and effective method. However, another significant player, which overrides energy in importance for certain processes, is entropy. We know that increasing entropy corresponds to the system moving toward equilibrium, and this is why the entropy of a closed system cannot decrease, as stated by the second law of thermodynamics.

Both energy and entropy seem to be fundamental parameters that drive the evolution of various processes that occur in the universe. Every change tends to minimize energy. Also, every change tends to maximize the overall entropy of the universe. At this point, we automatically question: Are these two statements equivalent? Or is energy more fundamental than entropy? Or does entropy get that honor? It seems both energy and entropy are on the same footing, but

depending on the particular system or process we are studying, one might play a more dominant role than the other.

Consider Brownian motion, the random motion of particles in a medium due to collision with the particles of the medium. Brownian motion can be understood in terms of both energy and entropy. The collisions, which are of a random nature, ensure a constant exchange of kinetic energy between the particles, and the system is in a state of thermal equilibrium, because the energy is evenly distributed throughout the system. In terms of entropy, the constant and random collisions between the particles ensure that the system is in the most disordered and random state, which is the state of maximum entropy. Let us consider another illustration: the mixing of two different gases. If we initially keep the gases separated within a container, the gases will inevitably mix over time. The initial configuration was a low entropy state. When the gases have perfectly mixed with each other, the system has reached an equilibrium configuration and its entropy is maximized.

Figure 17: Two different gases (colored red and blue), initially separated by a partition (left), will mix as soon as the partition is removed (right). (Source: Springer. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-3473-1_6)

Does this mean the maximum entropy state is always achieved when two samples are mixed? Not necessarily. Let us look at polymers. Polymers are connected chains of smaller chemical units, and they form an integral part of many essential components that comprise living organisms. When two polymer chains are kept in a mixed state in a confined volume, they are often found to *spontaneously* separate [31].

Given the physical dimension of polymers, one might expect them to exhibit Brownian motion, but polymers do not always mix (for instance, under confinement). Systems usually try to minimize their free energy, which is defined as $U - TS$, where U is the internal energy, T is the temperature and S is the entropy of the system. The minimization of free energy is achieved through subtle changes in the internal energy U and the entropy S . From the expression for free energy ($U - TS$), it is clear that the free energy can be minimized both by minimizing the internal energy U or maximizing the entropy S , and entropy will play a more dominant role at higher temperatures.

Figure 18: Linear polymer chains suspended in a liquid medium, observed under a microscope. (Source: Wikipedia.)

Let us consider two polymer chains, confined within a fixed volume. Minimizing internal energy becomes less important than maximizing the entropy here, because the degrees of freedom available to the polymers are already constrained by the volume they are confined within, and the kinetic energies of the polymers cannot vary much. The polymers will try to arrange themselves in a configuration that has the maximum entropy, within this volume. The crucial difference between the system of gas molecules and polymers is that gas molecules are free particles, whereas polymers are connected chains. If the polymers are initially in a mixed state and kept in a confined volume, they cannot effectively vibrate, leading to a decrease in the number of possible configurations, and hence a decrease in entropy. On the other hand, if within the same confined volume the polymers are separate, they can vibrate more freely, indicating a higher number of possible configurations and a higher entropy.

Figure 19: Two polymer chains (colored red and blue) confined to a fixed volume and initially in a mixed state (left) will separate spontaneously to achieve the highest entropy state (right). (Source: Springer. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-3473-1_6)

Naively, it might appear that the mixed state is a higher entropy state, but that is not so. This is why polymers confined to a fixed volume separating spontaneously is not really surprising, because this favors an increase in the configurational entropy of the polymers. Let us consider a related, but different scenario. When we heat most objects, they usually expand. At high temperatures, we know that entropy maximization becomes more important than minimizing internal energy as stated by the free energy expression $U - TS$. Expansion means more volume becomes available to the microscopic constituents (atoms) of the object being heated, and hence entropy increases. However, rubber bands are found to contract on heating. Rubber bands are basically networks of polymer chains. When a rubber band is heated, it contracts so that the polymer chains coil up into a disordered configuration that has a higher entropy. If the rubber band expanded, the polymers would be in a stretched-out configuration, which has a lower entropy. The situation here is different from the case we considered above, where the polymers were confined to a fixed volume. But in both cases, the system tries to maximize entropy.

Figure 20: The unstretched configuration of polymers in a rubber band shown above has a higher entropy as compared to the stretched configuration below. (Source: Royal Society of Chemistry.)

The above examples beautifully illustrate how studying the world around us through the lens of energy and entropy sheds light on a wide range of phenomena, some of them counterintuitive at first glance. However, other than energy and entropy, there is another important player that deserves mention: symmetry. Although unlike energy and entropy, symmetry is a more abstract parameter whose effects are often not explicitly apparent, it is nevertheless a very important concept in physics.

A symmetry is essentially a transformation under which the object being transformed remains unchanged in some respect(s). For example, rotating an

equilateral triangle by 120 degrees does not change the orientation of the triangle (so here, it is the orientation that remains symmetric under the transformation). Similarly, flipping the equilateral triangle along a perpendicular line joining one of its vertices to the opposite side does not change its orientation either. And if we leave the equilateral triangle as it is (do nothing to it), again its orientation does not change.

Figure 21: Symmetries of an equilateral triangle. (Source: Quanta Magazine.)

We have a very important and fundamental theorem – Noether’s theorem [32], proposed by Emmy Noether – which says that associated with every symmetry, there is a conserved quantity. Time symmetry, for instance, is associated with the conservation of energy. Time symmetry, in very simple terms, means that the laws of physics do not change with time. If we perform an experiment now and two days later, under exactly the same external conditions, we do not expect different results. This is because we implicitly assume time symmetry (the laws of physics would be the same two days from now as it is today). Let us say we are interested in measuring the weight of an object, which is just the product of its mass and the acceleration due to gravity, both of which are constants at a fixed point in space. Thus, we do not expect the weight of the object to change with time, as long as

we do not move the object. Let us assume this was not the case (in other words, assume there was no time symmetry). That implies it would take different amounts of energy to lift this object up at different points in time, since its weight changes with time. We would need to spend the least amount of energy if we lift the object up when its weight is minimum. However, if we keep track of the object's weight and drop the object from some height at a later time when its weight is higher than what it was when it was lifted, we would generate more energy from dropping the object than we had used to lift it. Clearly, this is a violation of the law of conservation of energy. This means energy cannot be conserved if there is no time symmetry. Of course, this is not a rigorous proof of the connection between time symmetry and the law of conservation of energy. However, it serves as an effective, qualitative illustration.

We will now study a very interesting phenomena: spontaneous symmetry breaking. A very useful way to think of symmetries is by asking whether we can distinguish the system in different directions, different points in space or at different times. If we can, we say symmetry has been broken. We can break the symmetry of a system by changing its physical properties (explicit symmetry breaking), for instance, by distorting one side of an equilateral triangle. However, in spontaneous symmetry breaking, the symmetry is broken in a more subtle way [33, 34]. Consider the figure below. From the peak position, the system appears the same in all directions, and the symmetry is unbroken. However, from the lower position, clearly the symmetry is broken, because the system does not appear the same if we look to the left and then to the right.

Figure 22: Illustration of spontaneous symmetry breaking. (Source: Condensed Concepts.)

Spontaneous symmetry is broken spontaneously (as the name suggests) as the system evolves following the laws of physics, even though these laws do not change. It is important to understand that symmetry does not only refer to the symmetry of things, but also the symmetry of laws. By symmetry of laws, we mean that even if certain properties of the particles or fields change in a certain manner, the laws governing those particles or fields do not change. Spontaneous symmetry breaking plays a particularly important role in quantum field theory, which provides a mathematical framework for describing how elementary particles interact with one another and gives rise to the fundamental forces (except gravity, which is something that cannot be explained in the framework of quantum field theory). It is believed that the four fundamental forces we see today were unified in the early universe. The energy and temperature of the early universe were extremely high. As the universe expanded and cooled down over time, the unified 'superforce' is thought to have separated into the distinct forces that we see today, due to spontaneous symmetry breaking.

All of this is speculative, and somewhat detached from the world around us. We see that symmetry is broken spontaneously as the universe cools down and its energy decreases. But do we observe this around us too, in conditions that are not as extreme as the early universe? Yes, we do!

Let us look at the three phases of water: solid ice, liquid water and gaseous water vapor. We will try to understand the interplay between energy, entropy and symmetry as water transitions between these phases. Breaking of symmetry is, in general, essential for stability. As the universe cools down and attains a more stable configuration (as compared to the early universe configuration which was highly unstable), symmetry is spontaneously broken. Similarly, even in the process of gaseous water vapor cooling and condensing into liquid water, and then liquid water further solidifying into ice, the symmetry of the system decreases. It is crucial to understand exactly why. Let us, for a moment, focus on solids, liquids and gases in general, instead of ice, water and water vapor. We know that solids have a crystalline structure, which appears to be highly symmetric (it looks the same everywhere). In solids, the atoms are arranged in an ordered, periodic manner. Essentially, this structure can be generated by taking a cube and stacking similar cubes on all of its faces perfectly, and repeating the process in all directions, for all the faces of the cubes that have not yet been covered. In simpler terms, start with a cube, and keep on adding similar cubes in all directions and repeat the pattern. The vertices of the cubes are the positions of the atoms of the solid within the structure. This structure is definitely symmetric; it has *discrete* translational symmetry.

Figure 23: This is a simple cubic lattice structure in three dimensions, which can be generated by starting with one cubic unit (the colored box) and 'repeating' it in all directions. (Source: Chemistry LibreTexts.)

To better illustrate the symmetry, let us assume that this structure extends infinitely in all directions (Figure 24). We can move from any lattice point (the vertices of the cubes) to any other lattice point, but we cannot end up at any other point within the structure (for instance, points on the edge of the cube except the vertices, or in the interior of the cube). The symmetry associated with this structure is discrete because we are not allowed to move continuously within the structure, we can only occupy positions separated by a discrete distance (the vertices of the cube).

Figure 24: An infinite simple cubic structure in three dimensions. (Source: Wikipedia.)

Clearly, since the above structure extends infinitely in all directions, it appears exactly the same everywhere, and from every lattice point, the structure would look the same in all directions as well. This shows that the structure is symmetric. It possesses discrete translational symmetry; if we translate or shift between lattice points, the structure still appears the same. This illustrates the symmetry possessed by a solid, although we should keep in mind that real solids do not extend infinitely in all directions, and can have imperfections in their lattice structure.

Now, let us consider a system of an infinite number of gas particles, extending infinitely in all directions. The gas particles are free, unlike atoms in a solid. Hence, they move about randomly, colliding with one another. This system possesses *continuous* translational symmetry; there is no restriction on the motion of the gas particles. The gas looks the same from *every* point within this infinite box of gas. If we are lost in this box filled with an infinite number of gas particles and extending away indefinitely in all directions, everything around us would appear exactly the same, regardless of where we are within the system, or which way we look. This shows why gas, in general, is more symmetric than solid.

Figure 25: An infinite system of gas, in which a very large (infinite) number of gas particles are uniformly distributed throughout. (Created using Python.)

Although we considered infinite solids and gases in our discussion above, we now qualitatively understand why symmetry decreases as gaseous water vapor cools down into solid ice. In general, symmetry is lost as a system cools down and its energy decreases.

Let us now think about solids and gases in terms of entropy and energy. Clearly, the system of gas described above has a higher entropy than the solid. The gas particles are free to move throughout the system, and thus the number of possible configurations is much higher in the gas as compared to the solid, where the solid atoms are bound to the lattice points and cannot move about freely. This means gas has a higher entropy than solid. The crystalline structure of solids is a highly ordered structure, indicating low entropy. We also know that being at a higher temperature, gas generally has more energy than solid. Of course, the gas particles can move more freely than the solid atoms, and hence have a much higher average kinetic energy than the solid. At this point, one might ask how is it possible for gases to have more energy than solids, and also have a higher entropy than solids. It seems that a high entropy state corresponds to low energy, because such a state would be very close to equilibrium. Let us first frame an interesting, but incorrect answer to this question. It is true that gas has higher entropy than solid. However, in a system of gas with a uniform density of gas particles, the energy is evenly distributed *continuously* throughout the entire system. For solid, we have a discrete crystalline lattice, and the energy is concentrated in the lattice points only (which are occupied by the solid atoms) and not uniformly distributed. This argument does not provide a satisfactory answer to the question. The real reason is rather simple. When gas turns to solid (directly or via the liquid phase), a part of the internal energy of the gas is released as heat into the surroundings, which is why ice (solid) has low energy than gas. The entropy of ice is also lower than that of gas, but due to heat being released into the surroundings, the overall entropy of the universe still increases. There is, thus, no contradiction.

Studying the subtle interplay between a system's energy, entropy and symmetry is a beautiful and highly effective way to analyze the behavior of a wide variety of systems and potentially draw fundamental insights about the way the universe works. Energy, entropy and symmetry are all extremely important players, and studying how these parameters are related to one another is not just interesting, but an effective method to investigate the complex world around us. The very fact that we have been able to identify parameters like energy, entropy and symmetry that can explain so much is surprising in its own right. But what is perhaps even more exciting is how much more of the universe we can explore and understand. The intricate dance between these parameters keeps the wheels of the universe rolling. And even though the universe might be headed for that uninteresting equilibrium state we have previously discussed, where nothing can occur anymore, it is still true that if it was not for the universe's overall tendency to minimize its energy, maximize its entropy and break symmetry in the process, we would not be here pondering this right now!

Appendix B: Black Holes, Information and the Future of Physics

Even though physicists were forced to give up on the dream of a deterministic universe once Heisenberg discovered the uncertainty principle, they still hope to explain the universe at all scales using a single theoretical framework. Today, we have two successful theories in physics – general relativity and quantum field theory – which seem incompatible with each other. General relativity describes the force of gravity and explains the large-scale structure and behavior of the universe. Quantum field theory studies the interaction between the elementary particles that make up everything in the universe, and describes all the three fundamental forces except gravity (namely electromagnetic, weak nuclear and strong nuclear forces). Although both these theories are extremely successful in their respective domains, and boast remarkable experimental support, they work with fundamentally different theoretical frameworks. All attempts to unify these theories – be it trying to find a quantum mechanical description of gravity or explaining the other forces in a framework that works with general relativity – have so far been met with disappointment. Many inconsistencies, paradoxes and unacceptable results keep cropping up whenever we try to unify these two pillars of modern physics, one of which is the black hole information paradox. This is a fundamental paradox in theoretical physics, and although this paradox has not yet been fully resolved, it has generated many fundamental insights about the universe. The information paradox is significant because it arises when we attempt to ‘combine’ general relativity and quantum field theory – the two pillars of modern physics.

We know, from Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle, that the uncertainties in the measurements of position and momentum *or* energy and time of a particle must always be greater than or equal to a non-zero constant. This means we can never calculate a particle’s position and momentum simultaneously with perfect accuracy (and the same goes for energy and time). Now, in quantum field theory, we have a quantum field associated with every elementary particle, which vibrates at specific frequencies. Particles are just excitations in their respective quantum fields, and the energy of the particle is determined by the frequency of vibration of their field, since energy is directly proportional to frequency. Even in vacuum, these fields do not remain still, but vibrate gently, giving rise to something called zero-point energy, which is basically the lowest possible energy. The lowest possible energy is not zero; the uncertainty principle allows for some fluctuations in energy. A consequence of this is vacuum fluctuations, which can cause a particle and its antipartner to pop up in vacuum for a short period of time

(antipartner of a particle has the same mass as the original particle, but has an opposite electric charge and differs in some other properties as well). Since the amount of energy in vacuum is randomly and temporarily changing at every point in space, vacuum is teeming with such particle-antiparticle pairs (called virtual particles) that pop up, and after a very short amount of time, annihilate each other and vanish.

Now, let us briefly talk about black holes, the existence of which was predicted by general relativity. General relativity describes gravity as a force arising out of the curvature of spacetime; the more the curvature, the stronger the gravity. One of the most notable predictions of general relativity is the bending of light when it comes very close to a strong gravitational field, or in other words, a deep spacetime curvature. Now, the mathematics of general relativity allows regions of spacetime with an infinite curvature. Such points in spacetime are called singularities. General relativity alone cannot fully describe a singularity, because at such infinitesimally small length scales, the effects of quantum field theory cannot be ignored. If light wanders too near to such a region in spacetime, which we call a black hole, it is sucked into the singularity. Nothing – not even light – can escape the strong gravitational pull of a singularity. In fact, since light cannot escape black holes and reach our eyes, we cannot directly observe these ‘holes’ in the fabric of spacetime, and they are called black holes.

Although Einstein’s field equations predicted that a sufficiently dense object would be surrounded by a surface where time freezes, and light, matter and even space would be sucked into a point called singularity where the gravitational field is infinite, physicists (Einstein included) did not initially believe that such objects actually existed in reality. It was then discovered that a symmetrical, perfectly spherical and smooth ball of dust could indeed collapse into a singularity. Again, this was swept under the rug under the assumption that probably nothing in this universe is perfectly spherical or smooth. But then, Roger Penrose showed that, according to general relativity, any distribution of matter, no matter how rough, could form a singularity if compressed into a very small volume [35]. Henceforth, the idea of black holes has been treated as a real physical possibility, and recently we have obtained experimental evidence that black holes do, in fact, exist. Black holes are characterized by a boundary in spacetime called the event horizon, which is often referred to as ‘the point of no return.’ If anything crosses the event horizon and falls into the singularity, there is no way we can bring that object back.

Now, let us ask a question that birthed the black hole information paradox: What if particle A and its antiparticle B emerge near the event horizon of a black hole,

such that A forms inside the event horizon and B outside? If this happens, then before the particles have a chance to annihilate each other, A is sucked into the singularity, and B remains. There is nothing to annihilate particle B. This question considers black holes (general relativity) and virtual particles (quantum field theory), and combines them and asks what happens. A little thinking would reveal the underlying paradox that is revealed by this relatively simple question.

Let us consider the situation described in the question. To someone outside the event horizon of the black hole (who has absolutely no access to whatever is going on inside the event horizon), it is as if particle B emerges out of nowhere and *stays*. It is not a fluctuation that can be explained by quantum uncertainty, it is a direct violation of the law of conservation of energy. Particles cannot pop up from nowhere and remain. The only logical conclusion is that the black hole radiates away part of its own energy, and this accounts for the continued existence of particle B. Essentially, the black hole radiates a stream of particles, and this phenomenon is called Hawking radiation, after Stephen Hawking, who first predicted this. As virtual particles would keep cropping up near the event horizon, the black hole would continue radiating more and more of its energy, eventually completely evaporating away!

Figure 26: We can think of the scenario discussed above as the black hole radiating a stream of particles, and we call this radiation Hawking radiation. (Source: Amélie Orban, Quantum Universe, Delta Institute for Theoretical Physics.)

The phenomenon of Hawking radiation, however, violates the postulate of unitarity in quantum mechanics. As we have already discussed, quantum mechanics demands that information must not be lost. But if a black hole

evaporates away over time, what happens to the information associated with everything that fell into the black hole (like particle A, and many other objects that were unfortunate enough to find themselves on the other side of the event horizon)? This is the essence of the black hole information paradox [36].

As far as we know, there is no way to retrieve information about something that has fallen into a black hole. It was initially assumed by some physicists that even though we cannot retrieve this information, it exists in some form inside the black hole, and does not violate unitarity. But once we learn that even black holes evaporate away, this possibility gets ruled out.

Fortunately, there have been a lot of recent and exciting developments in black hole information paradox research, although a complete resolution of the paradox has still not been achieved. Classically, it is assumed that a black hole can be fully described using just three parameters: its mass, electric charge and angular momentum. This is called the no-hair theorem. However, recent research suggests black holes are not as simple as proposed by the no-hair theorem. It is believed that when an object falls into a black hole, it leaves some subtle traces.

Let us observe that the assumption that an object that falls into a black hole is indeed 'deleted' from the universe violates the second law of thermodynamics; once an object disappears into a black hole, it is gone without a trace and so is the entropy associated with it, indicating a decrease in the overall entropy of the universe. A significant breakthrough in our understanding of black holes came when Jacob Bekenstein proposed that black holes have an entropy of their own, which is proportional to the area of their event horizons. According to Bekenstein, when matter falls into a black hole, the lost entropy is taken care of by the increase in the black hole entropy. This was a very crucial step that helped physicists achieve a better understanding of the black hole information paradox.

Physicists continued making impressive progress on the information paradox. Gerard 'tHooft demonstrated that particles falling into black holes could cause gravitational deformation or 'bumps' on the event horizon. The information of everything that fell inside the black hole could be encoded in these 'bumps.' 'tHooft proposed to treat black holes as holograms [37]; the information associated with all the three-dimensional objects falling into the three-dimensional black hole is entirely stored on the two-dimensional surface of the black hole (the event horizon). This means the three-dimensional volume inside the black hole is equivalent to the two-dimensional surface of the black hole.

Some physicists have taken this idea further, they have proposed that the entire universe could be a hologram, where gravity is nothing but a projection of

quantum field theory in a higher dimension. This idea is based on the holographic principle, which says that all the information within a volume of space can be completely stored in its boundary. In the context of fundamental physics, holographic duality is one of the best examples of the holographic principle. Holographic duality, arguably one of the most promising approaches to unify gravity with quantum field theory, beautifully links these two entirely different kinds of theories in physics. This means once we work out the details of any one of these theories (the easier-to-handle one), we essentially know everything about the other theory. Technically, holographic duality is also referred to as AdS/CFT correspondence, where AdS refers to Anti de-Sitter spaces (volumes of spaces with negative curvature), while CFT refers to Conformal Field Theory (a particular type of quantum field theories). The basic idea behind the technical jargon is simple. Let us imagine a sphere; we can think of CFT as the boundary or surface of the sphere, while the AdS space is the volume inside the sphere. Everything in the AdS space has a counterpart in the CFT boundary. Gravity only exists within the AdS space, and not on the boundary. The boundary is solely described by quantum field theory. This means it is possible to relate a theory which includes gravity in its framework to a quantum field theory which has no gravity, and this is indeed a promising approach to reconcile gravity and quantum field theory.

Figure 27: The AdS/CFT correspondence. String theory attempts to reconcile gravity with quantum field theory, and postulates that particles are fundamentally vibrating strings of energy. The no-gravity theory on the boundary, a type of quantum field theory, works with particles. (Source: Quanta Magazine.)

When applied to a black hole, which is believed to be a three-dimensional object governed by general relativity, the holographic principle claims that all the information contained inside the black hole (in other words, all the information of all the objects that fell into the black hole) is encoded in the two-dimensional surface (event horizon) of the black hole. Thus, information is preserved. We can define a quantity called the entanglement entropy, which can be thought of as a measure of the amount of information stored in the black hole. More precisely, the entanglement entropy is related to the degree of entanglement between the black hole and the radiation. According to the holographic picture, the entanglement entropy would remain constant throughout the lifetime of the blackhole, because all the information is *always* encoded in the boundary (event horizon) of the black hole. However, there is a problem here. As the black hole keeps radiating energy, the surface area of its event horizon would shrink, and so would the information contained in the black hole. The entanglement entropy cannot remain constant throughout the entire process (from the birth to the complete evaporation of the black hole).

Figure 28: The holographic principle predicts that the entanglement entropy of a black hole would remain constant throughout its lifetime. (Created using Python.)

The next important step was taken by Don Page, who realized that looking at the way the information emitted by the black hole and the information still contained in the black hole are connected would be a better idea. He proposed that the emitted radiation from black holes is quantum-mechanically entangled with its origin inside the black hole. If we look at the radiation, it appears random. But if we consider the entire system of the black hole as well as the emitted radiation, it

would probably be possible to retrieve the information of objects that fell into the black hole. Page found that the entanglement entropy is zero at the beginning of the process (when the black hole just forms), because there is no radiation to get entangled with at this point. And at the end of the black hole's lifetime, Page reasoned that the entanglement entropy should be zero again, if information is to be preserved (as demanded by quantum mechanics). This is not surprising; since there is no black hole remaining at the end of the process, an entanglement entropy of zero is expected. The entanglement entropy-vs-time curve for black holes, according to Page, is shown below [38].

Figure 29: The Page curve. Initially as the black hole is formed, its entanglement entropy is zero, and at the end of its journey, when the black hole has fully evaporated, its entanglement entropy drops back to zero again, meaning that information is preserved in the process.

(Created using Python.)

There are many other proposed approaches to deal with the information paradox that we will not be discussing here. We discussed the black hole information paradox because it arises when we try to unify two seemingly incompatible theories of physics, and as we have seen, studying the information paradox has generated great insights that went beyond the confines of just this problem and redefined theoretical physics. However, it would be foolish to deny that progress in fundamental physics in recent years has been painfully slow. Based on everything we know so far, what does the future of physics look like?

Albert Michelson is once said to have claimed that all that remained in physics was to fill in the sixth decimal place. All of physics, he believed, was essentially discovered; perhaps better accuracy could be achieved in the future, but there was nothing new to discover. Today, we realize how terribly mistaken he was. And even if, one day, we succeed in merging gravity and quantum theory to create a unified framework that describes all possible fundamental interactions in the universe, physics would hardly be over. Even if we have a complete picture of fundamental physics, the mammoth task of reducing the behavior of complex systems solely in terms of the laws of fundamental physics remains. We do not know whether that is possible at all, but at least this shows there is still so much more to do. Of course, one may question the famous saying that the more we know, the more we realize how much we do not yet know, because practically, existing knowledge puts some constraints on the unknown, making them easier to figure out. However, it is also possible that some features of the universe are not just unknowns, but unknowables, meaning they can never be explained in terms of more fundamental principles and they are just brute facts that must be accepted without questioning.

Humans have always strived to make sense of the world around them. The starting point of science is probably the realization that there is some regularity and predictability in the world. For instance, experiments always produce the same results if performed under similar conditions; in other words, they are repeatable. To explain the results of these experiments and other observations, we have tried to formulate universal laws that apply to a wide range of phenomena. From Newton's days to the present, science has built up our view of the universe, using the convenient language of mathematics. Just like green insects living on a tree can camouflage better than red insects and survive, beautiful ideas (that gather a good amount of experimental support) survive in science. A natural selection of ideas has helped us filter incorrect theories and move toward a universal theory.

A fundamental goal of physics, as we have already discussed, is to create a unified theoretical framework that would describe all the four fundamental forces in the universe. Mathematically, there could be many such frameworks, but physicists would be happiest if they can find a single, unique framework that does it all! Such a theory is popularly referred to as a theory of everything, which, many physicists believe, must unify gravity with quantum field theory (this is why such a theory is also sometimes called a theory of quantum gravity). The idea of unification is a fundamental philosophy in physics. For instance, with the discovery of atoms, ice, water, and water vapor have, in some sense, been unified into the framework of water molecules; all three are made up of the same water molecules, arranged differently. Similarly, we can study the electromagnetic,

weak nuclear and strong nuclear forces in the framework of quantum field theory, but it has so far been impossible to find a fitting description of gravity within this framework.

When we are forced to deal with objects that are massive as well as tiny, both general relativity and quantum field theory come into play. At such length scales, the notion of a smooth spacetime geometry, the central principle of general relativity, is destroyed by the fluctuations that arise out of quantum uncertainty. General relativity works fine for large distances and massive objects, when we can neglect the effects predicted by quantum field theory. Similarly, quantum mechanics works fine at small scales. One may wonder why we should even try to unify these two theories instead of just applying them to situations where they work. The reason is that we do not expect two fundamental theories of the same physical reality to be incompatible. The apparent incompatibility indicates that our current understanding of the universe is incomplete.

After Einstein published his theory of general relativity, he, along with many other physicists, started looking for a similar geometric interpretation of electromagnetism [39]. Back then, gravity and electromagnetism were the only known fundamental forces, the weak nuclear and strong nuclear forces have not yet been discovered. Theodor Kaluza soon found out that by assuming the existence of an extra, hidden dimension at every point in space, he could incorporate electromagnetism in a framework consistent with Einstein's general relativity. Later, Oskar Klein further worked on and improved Kaluza's ideas. That adding more dimensions simplifies the unification of forces is a fundamental idea in theoretical physics. However, why do we not see these extra dimensions? The reason is believed to be that these dimensions are curled up to very small lengths that not even the elementary particles can access. Let us look at a simple analogy. From a long distance, a very thin cylindrical pipe appears to be a one-dimensional straight line. To specify the position of a point on this one-dimensional line, we only need a single number, which is the distance of the point from either the left or the right end of the pipe. But if we zoom in, it would become apparent that in addition to moving forward or backward, it is also possible for a point on this pipe to move around the pipe in the clockwise or counterclockwise direction. So the pipe is actually two-dimensional. (If we cut along the length of the pipe and unfold it open, we would get a two-dimensional sheet.) The dimension that we can see even from a long distance – the one along the length of the pipe – is stretched and easy to see, while the other dimension is curled up, and difficult to see from a distance. Similarly, in addition to the stretched, easy-to-see dimensions around us, it is possible to have smaller dimensions which are curled up and inaccessible to us. Although Kaluza-Klein theories are mostly

incorrect, the idea of higher dimensional theories have stuck. In fact, one of the best candidates we have for a theory of everything – string theory – works in eleven dimensions!

Figure 30: A thin pipe appears one-dimensional from a distance, but if we zoom in, we find that it has a second, curled-up dimension in addition to the extended dimension. (Source: Wikipedia.)

String theory [40] proposes that one dimensional ‘strings,’ the different modes of vibrations on which correspond to the different particles, are the most fundamental building blocks of the universe. In string theory, forces are a consequence of strings joining and breaking. All forces and particles can be explained by assuming that the strings propagate in a fixed background in such a way so as to minimize the area taken up. String theory basically replaces zero-dimensional point particles with one-dimensional strings of energy. Replacing the concept of point particles with strings proved to be the crucial step in resolving the conflict between general relativity and quantum mechanics. Roughly speaking, string theory asserts that there is a smallest possible distance, distances smaller than which cannot be probed even in theory, and do not exist (in some sense). Strings are not point particles, they are smeared out; and by putting a lower limit on the distance that can be probed, we can avoid the conflict between general relativity and quantum mechanics (which arises when we magnify spacetime to very small scales).

The reason string theory is believed to be a strong candidate for a theory of everything is that although it was initially developed as a theory of the strong nuclear interaction, it eventually turned out that it was possible for string theory

to include all the three forces *plus* gravity in its framework. In fact, gravity *must* be included for the theory to work, as a requirement. This suggested that instead of just describing the strong nuclear interaction, string theory is in fact a theory that unifies all the four fundamental forces. One of the most preposterous claims of string theory (more precisely, M theory, which is a mathematically consistent and unified picture of the different possible string theories) is that there are eleven dimensions. It should be noted that although by dimension in string theory, we would usually mean the number of independent directions in which a string can vibrate, the eleventh dimension in M-theory is actually a hidden dimension of the string itself [40].

Loop quantum gravity [41, 42] is one of the most prominent alternatives to string theory. Loop quantum gravity attempts to apply the principles of quantum mechanics to gravity. General relativity describes gravity as a consequence of the curved geometry of spacetime. Loop quantum gravity, however, suggests that space is not continuous, but quantized and granular. And unlike string theory, loop quantum gravity is background independent. This means we do not need to define a fixed background in loop quantum gravity; the properties of the background (spacetime) emerge from the theory itself. This is good, because this reduces the number of inputs the theory needs to make its predictions. String theory is background dependent; we describe strings moving in a fixed background (in fixed space and time). Theories like string theory and loop quantum gravity are often viewed, and with good reason, as abstract mathematical frameworks that might have nothing to do with the physical universe. We understand very little about these theories, and they have so far not made any feasible, concrete prediction that can be experimentally falsified.

Although a significant portion of theoretical physics research has been directed toward finding ways to consistently unify gravity with quantum field theory, a small group of physicists have explored an entirely different direction. They propose gravity might not be a fundamental interaction in the first place. Instead of trying to put gravity within the same framework as the other three forces, they propose that gravity can be understood as an entropic force, meaning what we call “gravity” is really a consequence of the universe trying to maximize entropy. Very simply speaking, the entropy would be maximized if two bodies come closer and collide, rather than if they move away from each other. If they collide, there are many possible ways the collision, and perhaps the subsequent disintegration of the bodies can take place, and many possible ways the parts can fly apart. Clearly, this is a high entropy state. If the bodies move away from each other and never collide, even though the bodies can occupy a lot of positions in space (an increase in the number of spatial configurations), the number of energy or

velocity configurations beyond the existing individual configurations of the bodies would be constrained. The idea of entropic gravity is not new; in his 2010 paper [43], Erik Verlinde argued that spacetime is emergent, and gravity is an entropic force arising out of changes in the information about the positions of the physical objects. In a recent 2025 paper [44], Daniel Carney et al. proposed various microscopic models that could explain the emergence of gravity. Quantum field theory describes how the electromagnetic, weak nuclear and strong nuclear forces operate between two physical particles (fermions) by exchanging particles called bosons between them. When it comes to gravity, however, Carney and his group model spacetime as a grid of qubits, each of which has a particular orientation. The qubits in the neighborhood of a physical object align themselves with the object; objects create a region of high order (low entropy) around them (since all the nearby qubits are aligned in the same direction). Now consider two objects, or in other words, two ‘pockets’ of order. Due to the tendency of the universe to maximize its overall entropy, these objects would try to come closer, essentially confining the order to a smaller region. Superficially, it seems the objects are pulling each other, as described by Newton’s law of gravity. Several models have been proposed along similar lines; the basic idea is to understand gravity as a consequence of the universe trying to optimize some parameter (like maximization of free energy of the qubits). These ideas, while interesting, are largely speculative. We do not yet have any evidence of these qubits, and assuming they exist, we do not know whether they really behave exactly in the way required for observed gravitational effects to arise, and if yes, why and how. Also, the models proposed so far only reproduce certain aspects of gravity that are already well understood. It is important to realize that the laws of physics are not really laws etched in eternity; they just describe the behavior of the universe well. We can build a thousand models that describe different aspects of the universe without any theoretical inconsistency, but without experimental validation, such abstract models are of limited significance in physics. And we do not know whether there even exists a single law describing every aspect of the universe. As we have seen, even the law of increasing entropy – perhaps one of the most universal laws we have – is actually a statistical law. Based on current understanding, the universe can probably be best thought of as a system that evolves spontaneously, guided by some optimization principles, but not fully governed by them.

The different frameworks of theoretical physics, that become useful in different situations, is beautifully visualized in the Bronstein cube [45], which is a cube that resides in a three-dimensional space with the axes as G , \hbar and $1/c$, where G is Newton’s gravitational constant, \hbar is reduced Planck’s constant and c is the

speed of light in vacuum. All of these are believed to be fundamental constants of the universe. The Bronstein cube is shown below (Figure 31). Note that this is only a very rough description of the different theoretical frameworks in physics. The origin represents classical mechanics, the starting point of all of physics. If we move from the origin along the G -axis, we arrive at Newtonian gravity, which is a classical, non-relativistic theory of gravity. If we move from the origin along the $1/c$ -axis, we arrive at special relativity, which describes how perceptions in length and time vary between different observers moving at different velocities with respect to one another. These effects become apparent only when the velocities involved are sufficiently high, close to the speed of light in vacuum, c . General relativity is a relativistic theory of gravity, and it is, thus, not surprising that we can reach general relativity if we move on the plane defined by the G -axis and the $1/c$ -axis. Essentially, general relativity can be viewed as a combination of Newtonian gravity and special relativity in the Bronstein cube.

Figure 31: The Bronstein cube of physics resides in a three-dimensional space of physical frameworks. (Source: *The n-Category Café*.)

If we move along the \hbar -axis from the origin, we are met with quantum mechanics, and if we move on the plane defined by the \hbar -axis and the $1/c$ -axis, we reach quantum field theory, which is a combination of quantum mechanics and special relativity. If we move on the G - \hbar plane, we reach non-relativistic quantum gravity, which, as the name suggests, is a combination of quantum mechanics and non-relativistic gravity (Newtonian gravity). And finally, quantum gravity (the theory

of everything) can be viewed as a combination of general relativity and quantum field theory.

We do not know when, or whether, our understanding would reach this coveted quantum-gravity-vertex of the Bronstein cube. It is true that progress in fundamental physics has been unsatisfactory during the last few decades. Let us think about the progress in the field of physics in the early 20th century and the early 21st century. In 1900, physicists were scratching their heads over blackbody radiation and ether. By 1925, we had discovered the general theory of relativity and much of quantum mechanics. In comparison, there has been no significant progress in our understanding of fundamental physics between 2000 and 2025. Of course, overall we have made remarkable progress; for instance, advances in Artificial Intelligence and the discovery of the Higgs boson. However, we have been unable to gain any fundamentally new, concrete insight about the universe. While this sounds discouraging, it does not necessarily mean that physics is facing a crisis or that today's physicists are dumb. On the contrary, it might indicate that we are reaching the limits of scientific knowledge! The more we progress, the more difficult it becomes to make further progress.

Another important aspect of this discussion is that in recent times, we are witnessing a widening gap between theory and experiment. Working on theoretical physics today is more likely to provide one with new insights in abstract mathematics rather than any insight about the physical world. It can no longer be said that theory and experiment go hand-in-hand, like it was during the early 20th century. This has led many prominent physicists to conclude that physics is currently 'lost in math' [46], and we should take physics back to its empirical roots. However, it would be interesting to explore a very popular idea in fundamental physics today – the emergence of spacetime – based on the possibility that mathematics might play a bigger role in physics than merely serving as a useful tool that describes physical systems in a compact and easy-to-handle form. The history of physics tells us that mathematical insights usually find their use in some physical theory sooner or later. It is indeed surprising how many abstract mathematical concepts, years after they were developed, turned out to provide the perfect theoretical framework needed to describe different aspects of the physical world. Even though many of us believe mathematics is a human invention, it is almost as if the world was created using mathematics. Eugene Wigner called this the “unreasonable effectiveness of mathematics” [47]. When linear algebra and the concepts of vector spaces, matrices etc. were developed so many years back, nobody at that time could think of any direct applications of these ideas in explaining the physical world. Today, however, we know that the entire canonical formulation of quantum mechanics is based on a certain type of

vector space, and eigenvalues and matrices offer us a well-defined mathematical way of predicting the possibilities and probabilities corresponding to measurements we make on a system in quantum mechanics. It is almost as if these mathematical concepts were waiting for the day we realized that they were just what physics needed to properly formulate quantum mechanics. There are more examples. The framework of quantum field theory and the Standard Model of particle physics is extensively based on the mathematics of symmetry groups, which was, again, developed many years back without any application in mind. Although Tegmark's mathematical universe hypothesis [48] sounds crazy to many, all of this could be suggestive of the fact that probably everything in the physical world has a mathematical description. Tegmark takes the argument further: the universe is not just described by mathematics; the universe *is* mathematics!

According to the idea of Platonism, mathematics is not invented by humans; we are only discovering the mathematical truths, but they have always been there and will always be there, regardless of whether the physical universe exists or not. In fact, we may boldly speculate that the physical universe could be a manifestation of some subspace of the most general mathematical space possible, and everything in the physical universe probably has a unique counterpart in this mathematical subspace. Even better, this correspondence could be one-to-one, meaning for every object in the physical universe, there exists a unique corresponding object in this subspace. A mathematical space simply refers to a set of mathematical objects that follow certain mathematical rules among themselves. These objects are not physical objects; they could be abstract mathematical structures which cannot be perceived by our senses. In other words, we can only see them in the equations we write.

Now, let us discuss a specific point where mathematics can potentially directly help physics: explaining the emergence of spacetime [49, 50]. Since general relativity and quantum field theory seem to work with fundamentally incompatible descriptions of spacetime, a lot of physicists speculate that spacetime is not fundamental, rather it is emergent from a deeper level of understanding. It is possible that this 'deeper level' has no physical description at all, because it cannot contain within it the notions of space and time (since spacetime is emergent *from* this level). It could be possible that underneath the spacetime description we are familiar with, there exists a deeper and entirely mathematical description of the universe, with no physical constraints. However, revealing this underlying mathematical structure, assuming it exists, would be no easy feat. We must keep in mind that it must not contain any concept of space or time within it; we must explain how the physical world around us emerges from

this structure. In particular, explaining the emergence of time would be challenging. Everything in the physical universe changes with time, but a mathematical space does not change in its entirety. In other words, its constituents and the relations or mathematical rules they follow do not change. We need to explain how this ‘illusion’ of change, and hence the notion of time, emerges when we focus on a part of the entire mathematical structure, the part which is the physical world.

Let us look at a second example of how mathematics might accelerate the progress in theoretical physics. As anyone with even the slightest idea of the incompatibility of general relativity and quantum field theory knows only too well, it is possible that we perceive the existence of some phenomenon in the physical world, or some aspect of a theory describing the physical world, which seems to violate some other theory describing some other aspect of the physical world. Now, it could be the case that this apparent contradiction would vanish if we shift to a more fundamental level of understanding, which can probably be achieved by mathematics. Mathematics is much more general than physics in the sense that it deals with the space of all objects and structures (which are following certain mathematical relations between them), and it does not exclude any possibility. Physics, on the other hand, is only concerned about those possibilities that occur in the physical world. This means by studying physics we can only see a part of the whole, and the contradictions that arise when studying just this part might be automatically resolved if we look at the whole (mathematics). A simple illustration – one with which we are familiar by now – could be the fact that open systems like living organisms decrease entropy locally, and if we do not take the surroundings into account (the whole) and focus just on the system (a part of the whole), it may seem that entropy is decreasing and the second law of thermodynamics is violated. However, the overall entropy of the universe, as we know, cannot decrease. Although it is not yet clear how to use this reasoning to solve the problems that arise when we attempt to reconcile gravity with quantum theory, the same approach (coupled with some good mathematics) might do the trick. In conclusion, the key to unlocking the secrets of the universe might not lie in devising better experiments and formulating theories based on the results of these experiments. Although this approach has been remarkably successful in past, the future of physics could belong to mathematics - the only place where truth and beauty mean the same!

So far, our discussion on the future of physics has been mostly focused on the hunt for a theory of everything, and fundamental ideas, like the emergence of spacetime. Indeed, when we think about the future of physics, the first thing most of us think of is probably the theory of everything – the holy grail of physics.

However, there are many, relatively new and interdisciplinary areas of research in physics – like complex systems, active matter physics etc. – which hold tremendous potential for driving the future of physics in new and unexpected directions. It is important and encouraging that scientists have been making huge progress in understanding complexity [51], consciousness [52, 53], emergence [54], nonlinear dynamics, artificial intelligence and so much more.

So many years back, Newton compared himself to a boy playing with ‘smooth pebbles’ and ‘pretty shells’ on the seashore. While studying just the smooth pebbles and pretty shells is not sufficient for understanding the ‘great ocean of truth,’ it certainly was a great starting point and stepping stone to a more general and fundamental level of understanding. Almost all of the physics that we know today stand, directly or indirectly, on the grounds that pioneers like Newton built for us. And in our own way, each of us are ‘Newtons’ playing with pebbles and shells, and venturing out on an endless voyage through the great and boundless ocean of truth. It is natural to lose sight of the endless wonders of the universe as we get caught up in routine work; however deep down, each of us wonder why we are here, and seek for an answer to this age-old question. While there is no doubt that today we understand much, much more about the universe than our ancestors, this elusive question ensures that science is still awe-inspiring and something more than just a routine field of inquiry.

From philosophers questioning whether they exist and mathematicians refining methods to study real-life phenomena to physicists discovering universal laws and biologists decoding the secrets of life: the story of science is a story of success and setbacks, courage and manipulation, practicality and elegance, and of our passion to unravel the fundamental secrets of the universe. And it is an ongoing story, with our generation as the current writers. So far, the story has been full of inconclusive results and unexpected twists. We have discovered new theories, only to learn that they were incomplete. We have made revisions to existing theories, only to learn that there was a paradoxical result somewhere. We have come close to finality, only to learn that there was still much more to discover. Currently, we are at a turbulent chapter of the story, faced with theoretical riddles (like quantum gravity) that seem unsolvable, and practical challenges (like climate change) that seem insurmountable. It is more important than ever that we take a tighter hold on the narrative and ensure the story progresses in the right direction. We need to ensure nobody is excluded from the wonders as well as challenges of science.

As a concluding remark, as scientists or science enthusiasts, it is extremely important for us to acknowledge the pressing challenges that we face that lie

outside the domain of standard science. These include social, cultural and political challenges faced by humankind as a whole. Owing to the sheer magnitude of the challenges facing us, collaboration is the only way to ensure humankind survives the transition into a new era of understanding and progress. The problems in modern science are so diverse, unexpected and multifaceted that significant progress can only be ensured through collaboration between scientists and experts from different disciplines. In the end, it is true that we are not special on the cosmic scale; yet it is us who have undertaken this quest to understand the deepest secrets of the universe – from its microscopic madness to its cosmic conundrums, and everything in between. As Sean Carroll put it [55], the universe might not care about us, but we care about the universe, and that is what makes us special. Let us take inspiration from the journey so far, and vow to contribute – each in our own unique way – in writing the future of science. The future of science could be exciting – only if we make it so!

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